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List of Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
CHIL	Control Hardware-in-the-Loop
CPES	Cyber-Physical Energy System
CRES	Center for Renewable Energy Sources
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DC	Direct Current
DER	Distributed Energy Resource
EIRIE	European Interconnection for Research Innovation & Entrepreneurship
EU	European Union
FS	Functional Scenario
GDS	Geographically Distributed Simulation
GUI	Graphical User Interface
JRA	Joint Research Activities
H2020	Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Framework Program
HEU	Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Framework Program
HIL	Hardware-in-the-Loop
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IEA	International Energy Agency
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IoT	Internet of Things
ISGAN	International Smart Grid Action Network
LAN	Local Area Network
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
MPPT	Maximum Power Point Tracking
NCP	National Contact Point
NTUA	National Technical University of Athens
PhD	Doctor of Philosophy
PHIL	Power Hardware-in-the-Loop
PV	Photovoltaic
RES	Renewable Energy Source
RI	Research Infrastructure
RT	Real Time
RTDS	Real Time Digital Simulator
SCADA	Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition
SIRFN	Smart Grid International Research Facility Network
SSO	Single Sign-On
TA	Transnational Access
TCP	Technology Collaboration Programme
THD	Total Harmonic Distortion
UCY	University of Cyprus
VA	Virtual Access
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This report presents the results and developments related to the provision of education and training material for e-learning and laboratory education of ERIGrid 2.0. The main objective of those activities is to develop and provide open source, online e-learning tools, material, and modules for laboratory education on project-related developments and identified topics. As part of the project's activities, an educational strategy is established for the identification of the target audiences, areas and topics of education as well as the advanced educational methods to be utilised for the efficient training on smart grids, smart energy systems and renewables research, which is used to guide and assess the impact of the training activities and developments.

Efficient education plays a critical role in promoting the energy transition. The new era of smart grids implies the increased digitalization of energy systems, thus people who study and work on topics related to power systems should be properly trained and develop new skills and capacities to deal with the contemporary complex environment and the interdisciplinary dependencies that exist in modern energy systems. The developed material and e-learning tools target university students, young researchers, and professionals. The educational topics and areas are identified as part of the educational strategy and cover a wide range of aspects related to smart grids. The tools and material delivered comprise five webinars, three educational tools, one interactive notebook, three virtual labs and one remote lab, one video and a couple of presentations. Furthermore, a Massive Open Online Course is under development as well as two laboratory modules.

More specifically, the delivered webinars cover the topics of remote testing, recent research trends in engineering and validation of cyber-physical energy systems, new co-simulation features of Mosaik 3.0, growing complexity of power and energy systems through the interconnection of geographically distributed research laboratories, RICH Europe, and Research Infrastructure access opportunities. Moreover, the tools educate the learners on load flow execution in Python, energy analysis for microgrids and islanded power systems, and smart grid applications leveraging machine learning principles. The developed Jupyter interactive notebooks allow the power flow calculation in transmission networks, using MATLAB and Python programming languages. The virtual labs offer the possibility of virtual access to solar-plus-storage system environmental and performance measurements, virtual access to microgrid and real-time measurements as well as virtual access to Photovoltaic models and related environmental measurements. Apart from the virtual labs, remote access is provided to an experimental microgrid for the online execution of experiments.

Additional educational material, including an introductory video about ERIGrid 2.0 activities and the slides from a tutorial regarding the latest digitally-enhanced methods and technologies used to enable the necessary observability and control of underlying Distributed Energy Resource assets in smart grids, are provided. Finally, the Massive Open Online Course will consist of six seminars and will cover topics on technical developments and validation methods in modern power and energy systems. The developed material and tools are publicly available at the dedicated section of the ERIGrid 2.0 website, in order to provide an online resource centre that is easily accessible to interested individuals.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

To foster the energy transition and adapt to the challenges arising from the rapid change in the power and energy sector it is crucial to update university curricula and appropriately educate the students, young researchers, and professionals (Hu, Li, & Chen, 2015). New skills and extended knowledge on areas that before were out of scope, like Information and Communications Technology (ICT), programming, etc., are necessary to tackle the interdisciplinary aspects of complex power systems. Technological advances available today can be leveraged to create e-learning tools and provide hands-on laboratory education that bridges the gap between theory and the real-world (Kotsampopoulos et al., 2014).

In this context, the work described in this report and the available material in the corresponding education section on the ERIGrid 2.0 website¹ aim to:

- Update academic curricula with new tools and methods,
- Provide tools and material to researchers and professionals to support understanding of modern power systems and promote research,
- Provide hands-on laboratory education to bridge the gap between theory and real-world,
- Help individuals build new skills, capacities and an inter-disciplinary background,
- Utilise learner-centred educational methodologies such as challenge-based learning and experience-based learning to support the development of problem-solving skills and out-of-the-box thinking,
- Improve the existing education practices by making use of procedures and methodologies developed in the ERIGrid 2.0 project, and
- Promote replicability of the developed tools and methods.

Thus, a variety of educational tools and approaches are presented in this report.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows: Section 2 identifies the training needs for modern power and energy systems, describes the motivation of ERIGrid 2.0 and the complex environment as a consequence of the energy transition, and provides a brief description of the procedure for the establishment of the educational strategy. Section 3 gives an overview of the developed e-learning material, and presents the modules and hands-on laboratory education that are under development. The report is concluded in Section 4. Finally, additional information about the developed educational material is provided in the Appendix A and Appendix B.

¹<https://erigrd2.eu/education>

2 Identification of Training Needs

2.1 Background and Motivation

The main goal and scope of ERIGrid 2.0 are to support the research, technology development, and innovation of smart grid and energy systems concepts and solutions in Europe taking a holistic and cyber-physical systems-based approach into account. An integral part of this target is to provide system-level support and education for industrial and academic researchers in power and energy systems (i.e., smart grids, smart energy systems, integration of renewables) research and technology development to foster future innovation as well.

Earlier in the project, major trends affecting research, testing, and validation processes with a special focus on new aspects such as interoperability testing and digitalisation were reviewed and investigated resulting in the formulation of a set of high-level Functional Scenarios (FSs). The term scenario refers to a description of a possible future vision that aligns and creates a path towards the realisation of specific targets. For ERIGrid 2.0 those targets are (*D-NA4.2 Common Reference Test Case Profiles*, 2021):

- Alignment with the European Green Deal²,
- Further support on the technology validation and roll-out phases, and
- Further integration of Research Infrastructures (RIs).

Moreover, according to the ETIP SNET VISION 2050³ of the European Union (EU), the target is to create a low-carbon, secure, reliable, resilient, accessible, cost-efficient, and market-based, pan-European, integrated energy system supplying the whole economy and paving the way for a fully CO₂-neutral and circular economy by the year 2050, while maintaining and extending global industrial leadership in energy systems during the energy transition. According to this, renewable energy systems, electrification of transportation, integration of electricity with ICT and other networks (e.g., heat networks), creation of new roles and interactions in a market system, like energy communities, are components of the future Cyber-Physical Energy Systems (CPESs) to be taken into consideration in research, education, and training of the workforce.

All the above-mentioned aspects have been reflected in the definition of six FSs in the frame of ERIGrid 2.0 (*D-NA4.2 Common Reference Test Case Profiles*, 2021):

- *FS1*: Ancillary services provided by Distributed Energy Resources (DERs) and active grid assets,
- *FS2*: Microgrids & energy communities,
- *FS3*: Sector coupling,
- *FS4*: Frequency and voltage stability in inverter dominated power systems,
- *FS5*: Aggregation and flexibility management, and
- *FS6*: Digitalisation.

The developed tools aim to address educational needs related to the previously discussed topics. Earlier in the project, an educational strategy has been established to assess the educational learning objectives and the areas that are being covered, level of complexity and

²https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

³<https://smart-networks-energy-transition.ec.europa.eu/etip-snet-vision-2050>

specificity and provide guidance to future developments. More details are provided in Section 2.3.

2.2 Necessity for Inter-Disciplinary Background

2.2.1 Complex Environment

The increased complexity of modern power and energy systems, stemming from the intelligence being introduced to them due to advanced control and optimisation schemes, has created a need for deep understanding of topics from different domains (Strasser, Stifter, Andrn, & Palensky, 2014). Future engineers and researchers should form an interdisciplinary background, being capable of understanding different topics like, electric power, heat, ICT, programming, optimisation, control, etc. Thus, university curricula and educational practices need to be updated and adapt to the arising needs, providing a holistic and modern approach to the training procedure. Classical electric power engineering education usually emphasises legacy systems rather than smart grids and does not sufficiently provide hands-on experience and knowledge of modern tools and practices.

Apart from the component and system level understanding of power networks, other domains like economics, sociology, and politics, are getting involved together with the development of power and energy systems (Stirling, 2014). New roles and interdependencies are created between the various stakeholders (prosumers, energy communities, indistinct role of network operators, etc.). Moreover, user acceptance, reliability, resilience and ecological sustainability are other factors that need to be studied and taken into consideration for the production of practically realisable solutions. All these different domains synthesise the future power system that needs to be orchestrated and operated in an optimal and efficient way.

As it is understood, new procedures and methods should be followed in the designing, testing and validation phases of such complex systems. In Figure 1, a suggested multi-stage process is presented. The first steps of problem formulation and testing are usually realised by pure mathematical calculations. The more accurate and complete the representation of the CPES system is, the more complex it is to use analytical approaches for modelling and analysis. As a next step, pure software simulations can provide a basic level of understanding and observability of the system's response and behaviour. However, the couplings and interactions of different domains are usually neglected and the component modelling is based on average models and simplifications. On the other hand, advanced validation methods like Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL), co-simulation, Geographically Distributed Simulation (GDS), as well as hardware experiments can reproduce interaction dynamics close to reality. The above-mentioned advanced laboratory validation methods exhibit the great benefit of assessing the dynamic behaviour of systems and hardware to the almost full extent but at the same time in a controllable and safe laboratory environment. Also, those methods accelerate the time and minimise the risk towards the last step of the testing process, the actual field tests.

2.2.2 Addressing Learning Needs and Requirements

In the framework of ERIGrid 2.0, several types of e-learning material have been defined as useful means to facilitate educational and training needs. Those include the following main categories (Kotsampopoulos et al., 2020):

Figure 1: Steps in the testing process for smart grid components.

- *Educational/Training Tools*: Software programs that are used by educators and students to facilitate the educational process. Usually, they are designed for carrying out various types of analyses (steady-state, dynamic, etc.).
- *Interactive Notebooks*: Human-readable documents that contain code-based parts (Python, MATLAB, etc.) enriched with text elements (paragraphs, equations, figures, links, etc.).
- *Webinars*: Engaging online events in which a speaker or a group of speakers deliver presentations to an audience, which interact with them through questions, polls or any other interactive means.
- *Virtual Labs*: Interactive digitally simulated activities similar to the ones that take place in actual physical laboratories.
- *Remote Labs*: Online access to the physical infrastructure of a remote laboratory.
- *Other E-learning Material*: Videos, presentations, and any other relevant e-learning material.

The above types cover a wide range of different e-learning means, aiming to allow the delivery of a wide range of training activities.

2.3 Educational Strategy Establishment

One of the main aspects of ERIGrid 2.0 is the development of training and educational activities, which aim to inform a determined audience about best practices and the latest advancements in a set of areas related to smart energy systems, including methods, approaches and tools, validation, roll-out and others. For the establishment of the educational strategy, the ERIGrid 2.0 approach is based on the considerations below:

- A preliminary consultation process among the partners that will participate in the organisation of training activities can give insights regarding the topics of interest as well as the target groups, and other aspects,
- Training activities and modules can more effectively be developed by small independent teams, and
- The collection of feedback from the participants in the training activities can lead to significant quality improvement.

Having said this, the preparation of the training activities begins with the determination of basic aspects, such as the main topic to be addressed, the scope of the activity, the target group to

which the activity is directed (undergraduate and Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) students, power system or ICT professionals, high school students, etc.) and the main tasks to be carried out.

Furthermore, the so-called learning objectives are determined, based on the achieved understanding level of the target audience and the training objectives. Those learning objectives can then be formulated as concrete capabilities that the learner will possess upon successful completion of the training activity, and they are assessed based on Bloom's taxonomy⁴. Lastly, the activity format is determined by the organiser partner, based on the training goals.

Elaborate information and details about the development procedure and the educational strategy itself can be found in Deliverable D4.1 (*D-NA3.1a Report on the Training Workshops and Staff Exchanges*, 2023).

⁴<https://www.wbtsystems.com/learning-hub/blogs/blooms-taxonomy>

3 Developed E-Learning Material and Lab Modules

In Section 2, the types and categories of the relevant identified e-learning material to be developed in the frame of ERIGrid 2.0 are presented. In this section, an overview of the e-learning material developed and delivered during the first 36 months of the project (current reporting period) will be given. More specifically, in Table 1 a list with the developed software tools is presented. In Table 2 a list of the delivered webinars and their participation statistics, is given. In Table 3 a list of the virtual and remote laboratories developed is given. Finally, in Table 4 a list of other e-learning materials developed during the current reporting period, is given. More information about the various e-learning material developed during the current reporting period is given in the subsequent section.

3.1 Educational/Training Tools

In this section, a description of each of the ERIGrid 2.0 educational and training tools listed in Table 1 and delivered during the reporting period is presented.

Table 1: List of training and educational tools developed during the current reporting period.

Software Tool	Description	Developer
Open source load flow tool in Python	A load flow calculator was developed in Python that can be used either as an independent tool or as part of a composite tool calculator or control algorithm.	CRES
Power flow notebooks	Two Jupyter interactive notebooks were developed for power flow calculation in transmission networks, using Matlab and Python programming languages	ICCS
Energy analysis tool for microgrids and islanded systems	An open license that enables the user to conduct techno-economic studies on microgrids and island power systems.	CRES
Smart grid applications leveraging machine learning principles	An open license tool developed in R that demonstrates the use of data-driven machine learning principles for the implementation of solar-specific smart grid applications.	UCY

3.1.1 Open Source Load Flow Tool in Python

The specific tool was developed by Center for Renewable Energy Sources (CRES) with the aim to provide an easy-to-use, open source tool for the analysis of power systems in steady-state conditions. The tool was developed in order to be used either as an independent calculator or as part of a more complicated setup (e.g., co-simulation) or even as part of a control algorithm.

From an educational viewpoint, the tool aims to familiarise the user with the modelling and analysis of power systems, as well as the use of open-source code in order to extend the tool's features and functionalities.

The source code for this tool was developed using Python v3.6.4 and is structured in the form shown in the following diagram Figure 2.

Figure 2: Load flow tool structure including input and output data.

The structure of the tool is divided into three parts: one related to the input data files in *.txt format, one containing the Python libraries that execute the load flow analysis, and one containing the output data, also in *.txt format. The user can introduce the specific power system model parameters through the input data, which cover a variety of aspects such as grid parameters, initial voltages, etc.

3.1.2 Power Flow Notebooks

The power flow analysis problem is implemented through a Jupyter Notebook in this activity, aiming to aid its introduction to undergraduate electrical engineering students.

Using the Jupyter Notebook structure, the theoretical background and the implemented mathematical process are analytically explained at each step of the source code, which is also given. Additionally, the results are presented at the end of each step along with some graphics for the voltage, and the active and reactive power of the buses. A screenshot of the notebook is given in Figure 3.

Admittance matrix calculation

- Initially, all impedances are converted to admittances (9)

$$Z_{km} = R_{km} + jX_{km} \quad (8)$$

$$Y_{km} = \frac{1}{Z_{km}} \quad (9)$$

- Afterwards, the diagonal and off diagonal elements are calculated

$$Y_{kk} = y_k + \sum_{m \neq k} (Y_{km} + Y_{mk}) \quad (10)$$

$$Y_{km} = -y_{km} \quad (11)$$

The size of the admittance matrix is (n x n) in which n is the overall number of the buses of the power system under consider. Admittance Matrix's size is (4x4).

$$Y_{bus} = \begin{bmatrix} Y_{11} & Y_{12} & Y_{13} & Y_{14} \\ Y_{21} & Y_{22} & Y_{23} & Y_{24} \\ Y_{31} & Y_{32} & Y_{33} & Y_{34} \\ Y_{41} & Y_{42} & Y_{43} & Y_{44} \end{bmatrix}$$

```

In [34]: # Function for calculation of admittance matrix
def calculation_ybus(num_bus, line_data):
    # Initialize a matrix, nbus x nbus, complex type
    y_bus = np.zeros((nbus, nbus), dtype=complex)

    # Calculation of elements of the lines
    for line_data in line_data:
        p = int(line_data[0]) - 1
        q = int(line_data[1]) - 1

        ykm = complex(line_data[2], line_data[3]) # (4)
        bsh = complex(0, line_data[4])           # (5)
        ykm = 1/ykm                               # (6)
        y_bus[p,p] += ykm + bsh                    # (7)
        if p != q:
            y_bus[q,q] += ykm + bsh                # (8)
            y_bus[p,q] -= ykm                       # (9)
            y_bus[q,p] -= ykm                       # (10)

    # Return admittance matrix
    return y_bus

# Admittance matrix
y_bus = calculation_ybus(num_bus, line_data)
print ("Ybus=:\n",y_bus)

Ybus=
[[0.-15.j 0.+10.j 0.+0.j 0.+5.j]
 [0.+10.j 0.-15.j 0.+5.j 0.+0.j]
 [0.+0.j 0.+5.j 0.-15.j 0.+10.j]
 [0.+5.j 0.+0.j 0.+10.j 0.-15.j]]
                
```

Figure 3: The power flow Jupyter Notebook.

With regards to the educational procedure, initially, students are introduced to the Jupyter Notebooks platform. Following this presentation, the participants upload and run the power flow Jupyter source file in the platform step by step. In the Ybus realisation step, they are also required to fill in some missing parts of the code, to showcase their understanding. Additionally, they fill in and submit a questionnaire with the results of each step of the power flow problem.

It should be highlighted that the present tool was already integrated into the laboratory exercises of power system analysis (steady state) module of the 8th semester in the School of Electrical and Computer Engineering at National Technical University of Athens (NTUA).

3.1.3 Energy Analysis Tool for Microgrids and Islanded Power Systems

The specific open license tool, also known as Flexxy, enables the user to simulate the energy behaviour of microgrids and autonomous power systems under steady-state conditions. The use of this tool is highly relevant to scenarios where energy balancing is considered, such as in an energy community.

From an educational point of view, the specific tool aims to familiarise the user with the modelling and analysis of microgrids under steady-state conditions and how the system operation can be optimised in terms of cost and Renewable Energy Source (RES) production.

The specific tool is provided in the form of an executable application that allows the user to design the microgrid topology via a Graphical User Interface (GUI). A screenshot of this GUI is shown in Figure 4. Through this GUI the user can introduce specific energy resources and specify their parameters. Also, additional scenario parameters can be introduced and modified via this interface. The execution of the simulation tests provides specific results illustrated in separate screens such as the one in Figure 5, or they can be exported in the form of data files for post-processing.

3.1.4 Smart Grid Applications Leveraging Machine Learning Principles

The specific tool was developed by University of Cyprus (UCY) with the aim to present methods and tools that demonstrate the use of data-driven machine learning principles for the implementation of solar-specific smart grid applications.

Figure 4: Screenshot of Flexxy's user interface.

Figure 5: Visualisation of Flexxy's output results.

From an educational viewpoint, the tool enables the user to familiarise with supervised learning modelling and performance analysis of solar Photovoltaic (PV) systems integrated into modern power systems. Moreover, the tool facilitates the demonstration of data-driven principles for the implementation of smart grid applications for solar PV systems under actual environments (i.e., digital twin predictive performance models and solar generation forecasting).

The tool was developed using the R programming language and the source code is structured into the data preparation and fidelity, model development, performance evaluation and graphical representation modules.

The user is introduced to a detailed step-by-step procedure for the construction of high-performing data-driven predictive models by leveraging different machine learning techniques (artificial neural networks, support vector regression and regression trees). The user is also able to benchmark and optimise the derived predictive models by varying the input features, learning regime and model hyper-parameters.

Finally, the application of the constructed models is verified by the user by importing actual PV performance datasets and numerical weather predictions (i.e., *.csv format) as a PV power plant digital twin (i.e., optimally performing virtual replica) and in solar generation forecasting (day and hour-ahead forecasting).

3.2 Webinars

In this section, details about each of the project's webinars delivered during the reporting period are presented. In addition, Table 2 provides an overview of the webinar's participation statistics.

Table 2: Overview of webinars participation statistics.

Webinar Name	Registrants	Attendees	External Persons	Zenodo (30.05.2023)		Youtube Views (30.05.2023)
				Views	Downloads	
Remote Testing & EIRIE Platform	169	93	79	500	699	186
Recent Research Trends in Engineering and Validating Cyber-Physical Energy Systems	63	30	n/a	194	134	n/a
Mosaik 3.0 – Open-Source Smart Grid Co-simulation Framework	46	46	32	582	619	899
Addressing the Growing Complexity of Power and Energy Systems through Interconnection of Geographically Distributed Research Laboratories	n/a	614	612	n/a	n/a	7
First Webinar of RICH Europe on Transnational and Virtual access opportunities (TA/VA)	n/a	65	n/a	27	24	n/a
Design of Smart Grid Test Lab Infrastructure	n/a	30	25	n/a	n/a	n/a

3.2.1 Remote Testing & EIRIE Platform

ERIGrid 2.0 partners showcased the project's infrastructure and present the collected experiences with remote laboratory access. Also presented were the ERIGrid 2.0 Virtual Access (VA) to infrastructures with demos of two virtual facilities. Moreover, the Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Framework Program (H2020) PANTERA⁵ project presented the interactive multi-functional platform European Interconnection for Research Innovation & Entrepreneurship (EIRIE) which acts as the meeting point of all actors who are active in the field of energy research and innovation throughout Europe.

As a result of this webinar, the participants familiarised themselves with the scope of the ERIGrid 2.0 project, its Transnational Access (TA) and VA programmes and their available physical and virtual facilities. Likewise, the participants were able to witness the real-time demonstrations of two virtual services. In addition, the participants were introduced to PANTERA, its objectives and the planned outcomes of the project. The webinar was fully recorded (video and audio) and was uploaded to the project website as well as to the project's YouTube channel. A snapshot of the webinar recording is shown in Figure 6.

According to the event statistics, a total of 93 participants attended the webinar, of which 79 were external persons (i.e., an 85% external attendance rate). Other participation statistics

⁵<https://pantera-platform.eu>

Figure 6: Snapshot of webinar recording on “Remote Testing & EIRIE Platform” available on YouTube.

are summarised in Table 2. Additionally, the participants also had the possibility to clarify any questions in the Q&A session, which was a valuable opportunity for potential ERIGRID 2.0 lab access applicants.

3.2.2 Recent Research Trends in Engineering and Validating Cyber-Physical Energy Systems

A driving force for the realisation of a sustainable energy supply is the integration of renewable energy resources. Due to their stochastic generation behaviour, energy utilities are confronted with a more complex operation of the underlying power grids. Additionally, due to technology developments, controllable loads, integration with other energy sources, changing regulatory rules, and market liberalisation, the system’s operation needs adaptation.

Proper operational concepts and intelligent automation provide the basis to turn the existing power system into an intelligent entity, a CPES. The electric energy system is therefore moving from a single system to a system of systems. While reaping the benefits of new intelligent behaviours, it is expected that system-level developments, architectural concepts, advanced automation and control, as well as validation and testing will play a significantly larger role in realising future solutions and technologies.

The implementation and deployment of these complex system of systems are associated with increasing engineering complexity resulting also in increased engineering costs. Proper engineering and validation approaches and tools are partly missing until now. Therefore, this webinar (organised by the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) Industrial Electronics Society) discussed and summarised the main needs and requirements as well as the status quo in research and development related to the engineering and validation of CPES. Also, validation examples and short demos are presented. Finally, research trends and necessary future activities (from an ERIGRID 2.0 point of view) are also outlined. A snapshot of the webinar recording is shown in Figure 7.

Overall, 30 participants attended the webinar out of 63 registrations. Other participation statis-

Figure 7: Snapshot of webinar recording on “Recent Research Trends in Engineering and Validating Cyber-Physical Energy Systems” available at the Resource Center of the IEEE Industrial Electronics Society.

tics are summarised in Table 2. Additionally, the participants had the possibility to clarify any questions in the Q&A session, which was a valuable opportunity for potential ERIGrid 2.0 lab access applicants.

3.2.3 Mosaik 3.0 – Open Source Smart Grid Co-simulation Framework

Smart grid incorporates different domains and multi-energy networks, which have to be simulated together to get insights into their interdependencies. To combine simulation components from different domains, the open source co-simulation framework Mosaik allows flexible coupling and scenario creation. According to the ERIGrid 2.0 project objectives, it aims to support the research, technology development, and innovation of large-scale, smart grid scenarios. Hence, Mosaik is a useful tool for students and researchers to investigate basic to sophisticated co-simulation scenarios. In version 3.0 of Mosaik the discrete-event capabilities were extended to improve handling of simulators with different time steps and allow external events to trigger events in the simulation. For interested users within the ERIGrid 2.0 project and external users, an overview of the capabilities of Mosaik is given to allow them to apply it to their current and future research.

A webinar on “New co-simulation features of Mosaik 3.0” was organised by OFFIS on 29th September 2021 as shown in Figure 8. A total of 46 participants (of which 70% were external) participated in this webinar. The participation statistics are summarised in Table 2. This webinar focuses on the new features of Mosaik 3.0 for intermediate and advanced participants. Additionally, a general overview of capabilities and introductory tutorials are also shown, which help beginners to make the first steps with Mosaik co-simulation. Mosaik is provided as open source software and fosters community participation where users can ask for support, provide feedback, or contribute to the code via related tool website⁶ or directly at GitLab⁷.

⁶<https://mosaik.offis.de/contact>

⁷<https://gitlab.com/mosaik>

Co-simulation framework mosaik 3.0

Main features

- Discrete time and discrete event simulation
- Accelerated and real time capabilities
- Ability to integrate IP-protected components
- Parallel execution of components
- Scaling of simulations on compute clusters

Open source (LGPL)
<https://gitlab.com/mosaik> <https://mosaik.readthedocs.io/>

Utility ecosystem

- Simulation models
- Interfaces for simulation tools (e.g. pandapower)
- Wrappers for programming languages (e.g. Java)
- Wrappers for standard interface (e.g. fmi or OPC UA)
- Visualization and data storage (e.g. HDF5, Influx+Grafana)

Webinar "Mosaik 3.0 - Open Source Smart Grid Co-simulation Framework"

ERIGrid 2.0 - H2020 Research Infrastructure Project

Figure 8: Snapshot of webinar recording on “New co-simulation features of Mosaik 3.0” available on YouTube.

3.2.4 Addressing the Growing Complexity of Power and Energy Systems through Interconnection of Geographically Distributed Research Laboratories

With the increasing use of power electronics interfaced with distributed generation, the power system has undergone a significant transition from a centralised operation regime to a decentralised and distributed operation. As a result, the power system has become more complex, and the limitations of a single RI in terms of computation capability and power apparatus availability have been exposed. Although geographically distributed simulations have been proposed as a potential solution, their recognition and widespread adoption have been limited. Aligned with the project’s objective of supporting smart grid and energy system research and technology development, geographically distributed simulations techniques are an active area of research, and its state-of-the-art developments and breakthroughs within ERIGrid 2.0 are key enablers for addressing the simulation limitation of the single RI and supporting the investigation and experimental validation of the power energy system with growing complexity.

As shown in Figure 9, a webinar entitled “Addressing the Growing Complexity of Power and Energy Systems through Interconnection of Geographically Distributed Research Laboratories” was delivered by UoS as part of the “Smart Grid Webinar Series 2022⁸” organised by Smart Grid Operation Centre, IVE Engineering, Hong Kong on May 24, 2022. This seminar disseminated the research work undertaken as part of ERIGrid 2.0 with an emphasis placed on demonstrating the feasibility and applicability of geographically distributed real-time simulation techniques for the validation of complex power systems. In addition, the developments and advancements that are pushing beyond existing limitations of the geographically distributed real-time validation methodology toward high-fidelity, trusted validation of future grid solutions within ERIGrid 2.0 were presented to the webinar participants.

In summary, a total of 614 participants (of which 99.67% were external people) participated in

⁸<https://engineering.vtc.edu.hk/en/TomorrowsEngineerDetails.php?UEID=32>

Concluding Remarks

- ❑ GDS hold the potential to address some of the growing complexities we face with transition of power system
- ❑ Although proof-of-concept deployments are reported in literature, a number of challenges remain to be addressed.
- ❑ Collaboration through ERIGrid 2.0 Laboratory Access Programme or IEA ISGAN SIRFN Advanced Laboratory Testing Methods (ALTM) Task.
 - ❑ ALTM - mazheruddin.syed@strath.ac.uk

University of Strathclyde

ERIGrid 2.0
Connecting European Smart Grid Infrastructures

Free access to 21 labs across Europe:
<https://erigrd2.eu/lab-access/>

ISGAN
INTERNATIONAL SMART GRID ACTION NETWORK

Figure 9: Snapshot of webinar recording on “Addressing the Growing Complexity of Power and Energy Systems through Interconnection of Geographically Distributed Research Laboratories” available on YouTube.

this webinar. By attending the webinar, participants had the opportunity to gain insights into the most recent advancement and development of geographically distributed real-time validation methodology along with its taxonomy and real-world applications. In addition, the participants also had the chance to raise their questions in the Q&A session for further discussions.

3.2.5 First Webinar of RICH Europe on Trans-national and Virtual Access Opportunities

This webinar – the first one out of a series – was organised by the linked Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Framework Program (HEU) Coordination and Support Action (CSA) RICH Europe⁹ of National Contact Points (NCPs) related to RIs. The goal was to introduce running H2020 and HEU RI projects providing TA and/or VA to external user groups.

After the opening and introduction of the RICH Europe project and its activities by the related coordinator APRE, the ERIGrid 2.0 RI access opportunities were introduced besides the access provision from the three other RI projects called AHEAD2020, EVA-GLOBAL, and LASERLAB-EUROPE. The targeted audience of this webinar was potentially interested RI user group members from research/academia and industry. A snapshot of the webinar presentation is shown in Figure 10.

Overall, 100 participants attended the webinar. Other participation statistics are summarised in Table 2. Additionally, the participants had the possibility to clarify any questions in the Q&A session, which was a valuable opportunity for potential ERIGrid 2.0 lab access applicants.

3.2.6 Design of Smart Grid Test Lab Infrastructure

The webinar was organised and hosted by Fraunhofer IEE and aimed to give an overview of the design and layout aspects for setting up a lab-based smart grid test infrastructure.

⁹<https://rich-europe.eu>

The ERIGRID 2.0 RI Access Opportunities

Thomas I. Strasser

Coordinator H2020 ERIGRID-1/2.0
 AIT Austrian Institute of Technology

First Webinar of RICH Europe on Transnational and Virtual access opportunities (TA/VA)
 23 November 2022, online

© The ERIGRID 2.0 Consortium
 EU H2020 Programme GA No. 870620

doi:10.5281/zenodo.7348988

Figure 10: Snapshot of ERIGRID 2.0 webinar slides on “First Webinar of RICH Europe on Transnational and Virtual Access Opportunities (TA/VA)” available at ERIGRID 2.0’s Zenodo community.

First, the challenges related to pure lab/field testing of smart grid components were discussed, and right after the advantages of an integrated lab-based validation approach, like Real Time (RT) and HIL test setups, were presented. Next, the audience was introduced to the general design criteria that should be followed, and relevant examples were showcased. Later on, various application areas of smart grid test laboratories were presented together with real-world examples, like using Control Hardware-in-the-Loop (CHIL), Power Hardware-in-the-Loop (PHIL), and power hardware testing for component certification, using hybrid system test platforms for system testing and demonstration, etc. Moreover, the essential evaluation criteria of the testing results for all test procedures were presented. Additionally to that, the audience was briefed on an overview of the general requirements for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories according to DIN EN ISO/IEC 17025:2018-03. The webinar was completed with the conclusions, outlook and a Q&A session in which the participants had the possibility to clarify any questions. A snapshot of the webinar presentation is shown in Figure 11.

Overall, around 30 participants attended the webinar. Other participation statistics are summarised in Table 2. Additionally, the participants had the possibility to clarify any questions in the Q&A session for further discussions.

3.3 Virtual Labs & Remote Labs

In this section, details about each of the ERIGRID 2.0 virtual and remote laboratories developed during the reporting period are presented. Moreover, Table 3 provides an overview of the developed virtual and remote laboratories.

Figure 11: Snapshot of the Fraunhofer page with information about the webinar on “Design of Smart Grid Test Lab Infrastructure”.

Table 3: List of virtual and remote laboratories developed during the current reporting period.

Laboratory	Type of Lab	Description	Accessed Lab
Solar-plus-storage system environmental and performance measurements	Virtual lab	A virtual platform that allows users to access real-time environmental and operational data from the smart PV and battery storage inverters of a test-bench solar-plus-storage system installed at the UCY nanogrid.	UCY
Virtual access to UCY micro-grid real-time measurements	Virtual lab	A virtual platform that allows users to access real-time environmental and operational data from the UCY’s microgrid.	UCY
Environmental measurements and PV models	Virtual lab	A virtual platform that allows access to environmental and operation data from actual PV systems.	CRES
Microgrid balancing experiment	Remote lab	A simplified experiment that allows users to remotely connect to the experimental microgrid via a web-link and conduct balancing tests.	CRES

3.3.1 Solar-plus-storage System Environmental and Performance Measurements

The specific virtual lab provides access to users to the solar-plus-storage system supervisory dashboard of the UCY nanogrid. More specifically, virtual access is provided to the cloud-based supervision system dashboards that stream real-time (1-sec resolution) data from the smart PV and battery storage inverters of a test-bench solar-plus-storage system installed at the UCY nanogrid. The experimental apparatus and setup of the virtual lab are illustrated in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Experimental apparatus and setup of the virtual lab.

From an educational viewpoint, the virtual lab presents to users an environment to familiarise them with real-time acquired smart meter measurements (using Modbus TCP Vendor-specific and SunSpec protocols) that include the voltage, frequency, power (apparent, active and reactive), inverter temperature, charging/discharging power and operational status of solar-plus-storage systems. Users are further permitted to browse and export historical PV generation and battery measurements. In this domain, the virtual lab demonstrates to users the smart grid concepts of real-time distributed energy resource digitalisation, observability and supervision using smart inverters and interoperability (Modbus TCP Vendor-specific and SunSpec protocols). A screenshot of the online dashboard that provides access to users to visualise the data and conduct this experiment is exhibited in Figure 13. Finally, offering this virtual lab as VA it's under consideration and discussion.

Figure 13: Solar-plus-storage supervision dashboard of the virtual lab.

3.3.2 Virtual Access to UCY Microgrid Real-time Measurements

The specific virtual lab provides users with access to actual environment microgrid measurements from a utility-scale university campus. Specifically, an overview of the Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition (SCADA) system of UCY's microgrid is presented and access is provided to the cloud-based dashboards that stream real-time (1-sec resolution) microgrid energy production and consumption data from the installed network of smart meters. The acquired

smart meter measurements (using Modbus TCP communication interfaces) include the voltage, frequency, power (apparent, active and reactive) and power quality parameters (voltage and current Total Harmonic Distortion (THD), Crest- and K-factor).

From an educational viewpoint, the virtual lab presents users to an actual microgrid environment to familiarise them with real-time acquired power quality measurements and energy flows. In this domain, the virtual lab demonstrates to users the smart grid concepts of real-time observability and supervision at microgrid frequencies using a network of smart meters, data-acquisition devices and cloud-based supervisory dashboards. A screenshot of the online dashboard that provides access to users to visualise the data and conduct this experiment is exhibited in Figure 14. Finally, offering this virtual lab as VA it's under consideration and discussion.

Figure 14: Microgrid supervision dashboard of the virtual lab.

3.3.3 Environmental Measurements and PV Models

The specific tool provides access to a set of environmental and operational data from the PV systems located on the CRES premises in Pikermi, Greece.

From an educational viewpoint, this tool intends to familiarise the user with the operating characteristics of PV systems under different environmental conditions. The specific tool is divided into the physical setup and the web interface. The physical setup involves two PV systems installed at different locations at CRES as can be seen in Figure 15. Also, the meteorological data are provided by an experimental setup used for the long-term assessment of PV modules.

All measurements are collected by different data loggers and published online on a web page. A screenshot of part of this web page is shown in Figure 16. It is worth mentioning that, among other things, the user can choose the quantities to be shown by the diagrams, modify the appearance of the diagrams and even download selected datasets in the form of *.csv files.

Figure 15: Location of the two PV systems for CRES' virtual lab.

PV System At CRES's Parking Lot

The measurements concern a PV system of 4.845kWp system which is installed in a parking lot of CRES, at a tilt of 40° and South orientation.

(Drag an area for zoom, right click to reset. Measurements of a chart can be downloaded by clicking on the legend of the chart.)

Choose time period:

Figure 16: Screenshot of the web page used for CRES' virtual lab.

3.3.4 Microgrid Balancing Experiment

The specific tool is a laboratory exercise that allows users to remotely connect and control a simplified microgrid setup. The actual microgrid is located on the CRES premises in Pikermi, and the users can connect to it via a web link.

From an educational viewpoint, the tool aims at familiarising the user with the power balancing experiment as well as the overall setup that enables remote access.

The specific tool is divided into the physical setup and the web interface. As can be seen in Figure 17 the two power units used in this experiment are one photovoltaic generator and one battery energy storage unit. During the experiment, the user can manually modify the active power set-point of the storage unit in order to balance the production from the PVs. In addition to the active power set-point, the user can activate or deactivate the PVs when necessary and adjust the reactive power of the battery inverter in order to allow for more power capacity availability. The battery inverter communicates with the Node-RED SCADA application via RS485/SMANet, whereas, for the operation/supervision of the PVs two ESP32 controllers are used. Both the battery inverter and the ESP32 modules use MQTT in order to publish their data to a specific broker, which, in turn, communicates with the SCADA over the Local Area Network (LAN). The reverse procedure is followed for the control signals. A screenshot of the web page that allows the user to conduct this experiment is illustrated in Figure 18.

Figure 17: Hardware and communication setup for the remote lab of CRES.

3.4 Other E-learning Material

In this section, details about other ERIGrid 2.0 e-material developed during the reporting period and are not included in the above categories, are presented. Moreover, Table 4 provides an overview of the developed material.

Figure 18: CRES' remote lab user interface via the web link.

Table 4: List of other e-learning material.

Title	Type of activity	Description	Partner/Developer
About ERIGrid 2.0 – Connecting European Smart Grid Research Infrastructures	video	Introduction of the ERIGrid 2.0 vision, objectives, and related activities (incl. access activities)	AIT
Virtual Tour through the SysTec Lab	virtual lab tour	Brief overview of different testing facilities at the test center SysTec located at Fraunhofer IEE, Kassel / Germany	IEE
Advanced real-time supervision and centralised control of distributed energy resources in smart grids	lecture/presentation	The advanced real-time supervision and centralised control of distributed energy resources in smart grids is a tutorial relevant to the topics of grid modernisation for high renewable shares and optimal operational management of DER in smart grids.	UCY

3.4.1 About ERIGrid 2.0 – Connecting European Smart Grid Research Infrastructures

This kind of dissemination and education material provides a brief overview of the activities and services of the ERIGrid 2.0 RI project, its related objectives, and the access program. Two versions of the related videos (available via ERIGrid 2.0's Zenodo community¹⁰ and Youtube channel¹¹) have been made; one with and one without the link to International Energy Agency (IEA)'s International Smart Grid Action Network (ISGAN)/Smart Grid International Research Facility Network (SIRFN) Technology Collaboration Programme (TCP).

So far 150 views and 25 downloads have been made on Zenodo as well as 488 views on YouTube for the standard version of the video and linked slides. The IEA version got 62 views and 3 downloads on Zenodo as well as 477 views on YouTube.

¹⁰Standard version at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4276382>, IEA version at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5590237>

¹¹Standard version at <https://youtu.be/b5UIbVA0lhY>, IEA version at <https://youtu.be/yKgrCOsonrE>

3.4.2 Virtual Tour through the SysTec Lab

The Virtual Laboratory Tour through the Fraunhofer IEE SysTec test centre was part of the “Wind and Solar Synergy Week” primarily organised by Fraunhofer IEE, Fraunhofer ISE and the Universities of Kassel and Freiburg for Master students of the “Online MSc. Wind Energy Systems and Solar Energy Engineering”. The virtual lab tour was scheduled for around 1.5h and took place on Sept. 22, 2022.

The virtual lab tour provided a brief overview of different testing facilities at the SysTec test centre located at Fraunhofer IEE, Kassel / Germany:

- PNI – Testing Laboratory for Grid Integration
- Mobile UVRT/ OVRT Testing Equipment
- HST – Hybrid System Test Field
- TPE – Test Centre for Electromobility with PHIL test setup
- EMA – Electrical Machines Laboratory

The main outcome of the virtual lab tour was to provide a brief overview to students in the online Master course WES-online, how different characteristics (grid code compliance, performance, etc.) of DER units and smart grid components could be assessed, validated and demonstrated in a lab infrastructure.

In total 13 persons (11 external) attended the virtual lab tour.

3.4.3 Advanced Real-time Supervision and Centralised Control of Distributed Energy resources in Smart Grids

The tutorial was created and presented in the framework of the University of Cyprus training events for undergraduate and graduate students, Cyprus. The main goal of the tutorial is to present concepts of smart inverter controls and interoperability protocols, and illustrate the architecture of cloud-based supervision systems for distributed energy resource assets in smart grids: “Advanced real-time supervision and centralised control of distributed energy resources in smart grids” (UCY).

The presentation describes the topics of grid modernisation for high renewable shares and optimal operational management of distributed energy resources in smart grids. In addition, it introduces the main interfaces of interoperability in smart grids and exhibits the use of data information models for the implementation of supervisory and control functionalities (active and reactive power set-points, Volt-VAR and Volt-Watt). The training activity further provides a conceptual overview of real-time supervision and control open-communication protocols, grid-edge Internet of Things (IoT) devices and cloud databases focusing on the UCY nanogrid pilot. To this end, the use of communication interfaces and universal connectors to standard protocols (i.e., Modbus TCP) for interoperability is extensively described. At the end, the training activity presents the demonstration environment of smart grid concepts pertaining to renewable energy source interoperability, real-time observability of future power systems and the applications of centralised supervision and control in the smart grid domain.

3.5 Massive Open Online Course

As part of ERIGrid 2.0, a Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) is being developed. The aim of this activity is to encompass the technical and training developments of the project, in a unique open coursework material, that can educate engineers interested in the domain of smart energy systems.

3.5.1 Course Structure

As the aim of the present course is to highlight all the development of ERIGrid 2.0, the structure of the MOOC was based on the structure of the work packages of the project, while the title was selected as: Technical developments and validation methods in modern power and energy systems. In particular, the 6 seminars of the ERIGrid 2.0 MOOC have been defined as follows, with the respective relations with the project's work packages also noted.

- *Seminar 1:* Introduction to the ERIGrid 2.0 MOOC,
- *Seminar 2:* Multi-domain energy systems (related to JRA1 Work Package (WP)),
- *Seminar 3:* Hardware-in-the-loop validation for modern power and energy systems (related to JRA2 WP),
- *Seminar 4:* Geographically distributed real-time experiments for testing and validation of multi-energy systems (related to JRA3 and JRA4 WPs),
- *Seminar 5:* Effective design and documentation of complex test system setups – Practical guidelines and tools (related to the NA4 WPs), and
- *Seminar 6:* Industry's opinion.

Additionally, the VAs developed and provided as part of the project, will be employed for the validation of the technical content presented in the seminars. The current status of the Moodle platform is shown Figure 19, which is still under development, as the material for all the seminars described above is being prepared. It is noteworthy that a rolling procedure has been followed, with each seminar being prepared and delivered as soon as the respective WP is finalised.

Figure 19: Structure of the ERIGrid 2.0 Massive Open Online Course.

3.5.2 Moodle Environment

After an extensive review of available platforms that could host the ERIGrid 2.0 MOOC, the Moodle environment was selected (Kumar, Gankotiya, & Dutta, 2011). Moodle is an open-source course management system and virtual learning environment. Its open-source characteristic was of significant importance for the objectives of this MOOC, aiming to maintain its availability to interested users for free, even after the project's lifetime. Moreover, the available tools inside the Moodle environment were adequate for the MOOC's needs, i.e., video hosting capability, quizzes, grading, attendance reporting etc. Finally, there is a plan to incorporate the Moodle platform of the ERIGrid 2.0 project within the Single Sign-On (SSO) system used for the ERIGrid 2.0 VAs.

The under-development ERIGrid 2.0 MOOC in the Moodle environment is depicted in Figure 20, where the main sections (seminars) have already been created, while Seminar 2: Multi-domain energy systems has already been delivered and will be briefly presented in the next subsection, as an example.

Figure 20: Moodle environment of the ERIGrid 2.0 Massive Open Online Course.

3.5.3 Example “Seminar 2: Multi-domain Energy Systems”

Seminar 2 introduces the simulation of multi-domain systems and was produced by OFFIS, TUD, and AIT. It consists of three main parts. First, the motivation and background for simulation and in particular co-simulation in the context of the challenges of modern energy systems are given. Due to the increasing complexity of the system, different domains and timescales have to be considered and simulation has to integrate different models to allow detailed investigation.

The second part introduces the co-simulation framework Mosaik¹² and is subdivided into two videos. The first gives an overview and describes the architecture and Application Programming Interface (API) of Mosaik, while the second shows a tutorial for a simple Mosaik simulation. This tutorial demonstrates how models can be coupled with Mosaik and a simple co-simulation scenario can be executed.

The third part of the seminar shows the multi-energy benchmark as an example of a more complex simulation scenario to investigate the inter-domain effects of coupled multi-domain

¹²<https://mosaik.offis.de>

distribution networks. It contains two differently implemented co-simulation scenarios of electricity and a heat grid, which are connected by a heat pump. The scenario is accessible at Zenodo ([ERIGrid2/benchmark-model-multi-energy-networks: v1.0](https://zenodo.org/record/5444441/files/ERIGrid2/benchmark-model-multi-energy-networks-v1.0), 2021) and GitHub¹³.

The recordings are available on YouTube as shown in Figure 21 and are integrated in the Moodle environment. The total duration of the four videos is 1:44:23 hours. To make the code of the simulation scenario easily available to the participants, the binder service for hosting JupyterLab was chosen. On binder, the Mosaik tutorials¹⁴ and multi-energy benchmark¹⁵ are hosted and made executable and editable directly in the browser. Thus, participants can reproduce the simulation shown in the videos without installing the simulation software on their computer and change the parameters or the code of the simulation to gain a better understanding of the simulation.

Figure 21: Snapshot of recordings of Seminar 2 about co-simulation of multi-energy networks.

3.6 Modules and Hands-on Laboratory Education

In this section, hands-on laboratory modules that are under development are presented. The modules will be deployed in the RI's of the partners and detailed descriptions will be included at the online resource centre in order to promote replicability.

3.6.1 Real-Time Simulation and Hardware-in-the-Loop for Laboratory Education

The aim of this lab exercise is to acquaint oneself with the control and stability analysis of inverters and inverter-based microgrids. A system comprising three inverters that supply low-

¹³<https://github.com/ERIGrid2/benchmark-model-multi-energy-networks>

¹⁴<https://mybinder.org/v2/gl/mosaik%2Fexamples%2Fmosaik-tutorials-on-binder/develop>

¹⁵<https://mybinder.org/v2/gh/ERIGrid2/benchmark-model-multi-energy-networks/mooc-demo?labpath=Welcome.ipynb>

voltage loads is considered, powered by renewable energy sources like small wind turbines or photovoltaic-battery systems. The lab module consists of various tasks and builds up the level of understanding regarding the control and dynamic behaviour of single to multiple inverters. Initially, the simulation is carried out in a MATLAB/Simulink environment, where the student can experiment with parameters and understand control techniques. Later, a microgrid is modelled in the Real Time Digital Simulator (RTDS) at the Laboratory of Electrical Systems of the School of Electrical and Computer Engineers of NTUA, providing the opportunity for students to familiarise themselves with advanced laboratory experimental techniques. Some of the main tasks of the laboratory module are organised as follows:

- *Task 1:* Designing of inverter systems and simple voltage-current control scheme.
- *Task 2:* Designing of droop control and understanding of inverter's response in island mode.
- *Task 3:* Designing of droop control and understanding of inverter's response in grid-connected mode.
- *Task 4:* Designing of the 3-inverter microgrid and understanding of power sharing.
- *Task 5:* Identification of the stability boundaries and the impact of the droop gains.
- *Task 6:* Designing of generalised droop control scheme.

3.6.2 Conformance Test Procedures for PV Inverters

This module describes the conformance testing procedures of small-scale PV inverters, based on specific grid-connection requirements. The specific procedure involves 6 different tests in total. These tests include measurement of harmonic and Direct Current (DC) current injection to the grid, evaluation of protections (leakage current and over/under voltage/frequency), as well as efficiency tests such as converter efficiency under various operating conditions and Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) accuracy under normal or partial shading conditions. The scope of this tool is to familiarise the user with all possible requirements for interconnecting a PV inverter to the grid, as well as to provide an exemplary procedure and guideline about the hardware setup and steps the tester has to follow.

4 Conclusions

The energy transition and the transformation of legacy power and energy systems to “smart” grids is progressing daily creating the pathway to achieve the European goals. This transformation brings together new challenges to be tackled as well as implies the need for updating educational disciplines and adapting training methods. This report describes the complex emerging systems, the couplings with other sectors, like ICT, automation, multiple energy vectors, and suggests ways to address the learning needs and requirements in education. A suggested multi-stage method for the designing, testing and validation of complex systems is presented. Moreover, the procedure followed for the establishment of an educational strategy to collect existing educational experiences from partners, identify target audiences and provide directions for the content and style of the developed educational material and activities is briefly explained. It is also explained that laboratory education is crucial for better system understanding, more realistic system validation, and bridging the gap between theory and practice. As the required knowledge is too broad, educational methods such as experiential learning and problem-based learning can prove to complement effectively the traditional teaching methods.

The main part of this activity presents the developed e-learning material and lab modules within ERIGrid 2.0. The type of developments concerns mainly webinars, educational tools, interactive notebooks, virtual and remote labs, while other materials, like videos and presentations, are included. The webinars are proven to be an efficient way to disseminate the progress and introduce the learners to the ERIGrid 2.0 methodologies and activities. The interactive notebooks consist of great means for students to comprehend power system analysis methods, like power flow, providing a step-by-step explanation of the method and the obtained results while at the same time giving the possibility to learners to develop programming skills. The developed educational tools have proven to be very helpful for the users in order to familiarise themselves with the use of tools as well as to better understand the application of methods, like machine learning in a smart grid context. Moreover, the developed web-based virtual labs enthuse the students and interested users and arouse their curiosity by virtually conducting experiments in a safe and convenient way, as well as enhancing the education process of students who do not have access to laboratory equipment. The remote labs provide online access to actual laboratory installations (for both monitoring and control) enabling the users to experience real lab conditions. Part of the developed e-learning material will be utilised and framed as part of the MOOC, which will disseminate and provide a comprehensive understanding of the ERIGrid 2.0 developments and tools to a wide range of audiences. Finally, laboratory modules under development are presented which will be applied for the hands-on education of students in the excellent RI of partners.

The ERIGrid 2.0 approaches, developments and methodologies related to Joint Research Activities (JRAs) (e.g., real-time simulation, co-simulation, hardware-in-the-loop, geographically distributed simulation), are utilised for the education and training of learners in the topic of smart grids and facilitate the creation of an inter-disciplinary background. Additional e-learning material (based on – and not limited to – the JRA2, JRA3, and JRA4 work) are under development and will be delivered in the future, while feedback on using the online tools by the users will be obtained and the results will be compiled to improve them. The analysis of feedback and the potential recommendations will be presented in Deliverable D4.4 related to lessons learned while the new developments will be reported in the final periodic report.

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Appendix A: Activity Plans

A.1 Open Source Load Flow Tool in Python

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan Open Source Load Flow Tool

Overview

Hosting partner: CRES
 Co-organizing partners: N/A
 Planned date (approximate): July 2021

Type of Activity: Education Tool

Contact: Evangelos Rikos, vrikos@cres.gr

Short Description

A description of the selection of topics, the hosting partners, intended audience and why the course is relevant to ERIGrid 2.0

The specific tool developed by CRES aims at providing an easy and open source tool for analysis of electric power systems under steady-state conditions.

The specific tool is highly relevant to the ERIGrid 2.0 activities because, as part of the scenarios investigated in the project, analysis of power systems is very important. In addition, the analysis and use of various tools and methods for simulation/co-simulation (e.g., MOSAIK, PandaPower, etc.) make this open source tool very relevant since it has been developed in Python.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

Why is this training activity required? What specific outcomes of EG-2 are conveyed here?
 Link to appropriate studies, directives, project ambition, etc.

The specific tool is useful as part of the simulation and co-simulation approaches implemented in the project. Since a large part of ERIGrid 2.0 is dedicated to the analysis of electric power systems with open source simulation and co-simulation platforms, the specific tool is a good example towards this direction.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

As Training Objectives Describe the competences that should be conveyed to the learners in your technical perspective.

This module intends to familiarize the user with two aspects:

- Modelling and analysis of electric power systems under steady-state conditions and

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

- Implementation of open source code for this analysis with possibility of extending its functionalities and data interchanges with other tools

In addition, try to specify the expected learning outcome as “Intended Learning Objectives” – specific measurable abilities that the course is intended to convey. We will use Bloom’s revised taxonomy to describe the school’s objective – Appendix 1 has an illustration to reference

A student who completed this course is able to:

1. Implement a consistent steady-state (Load Flow) analysis for specific power system examples
2. Expand the tool’s functionalities towards adding more features (e.g., a Graphical User Interface, implementation in multiple timeframes, interfacing with other tools, etc.)

Outline of Training Activity

Describe here the key components and learning activities comprising the training activity. A time schedule can be included here if available.

The code for the tool is developed in Python3.6.4 and is structured in the form shown in the following diagram:

The structure of the tool is divided into three parts, one related to the input data files in txt format, one containing the Python libraries that execute the Load Flow analysis, and one containing the output data, also in txt format. The user can introduce the specific power system model parameters through the input data, which cover a variety of aspects such as Grid Parameters, Initial Voltages, etc.

Evaluation approach

How is the success of the training activity evaluated? Note EG-2 requests an evaluation only by the organizers (NA3-Training_Activity_Report_Form)

The success of the tool could be evaluated by the number of users/downloads of the source code.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.2 Power Flow Notebooks

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan < Power Flow Jupyter Notebooks >

Overview

Hosting partner: ICCS-NTUA

Co-organizing partners: -

Planned date (approximate): December 2021/2022

Type of Activity: Laboratory Exercise for undergraduate students

Contact: Alkistis Kontou (alkistiskont@gmail.com)

Short Description

The power flow problem in Jupyter Notebooks was integrated in the first laboratory exercise of Power System Analysis (Steady State) Course in the 8th semester of the School of Electrical and Computer Engineering at National Technical University of Athens.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

Using the Jupyter notebook structure, the implemented mathematical process is theoretically explained at each step of the source code. Additionally, the results are presented at the end of each step along with some graphics for the voltage, the active and reactive power of the buses.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

As Training Objectives Describe the competences that should be conveyed to the learners in your technical perspective.

This module intends to:

1. Familiarize students with the mathematical process for the power flow calculation and solving
2. Analyze the operation of power systems under steady-state
3. Familiarize students with useful programming tools like Jupyter Notebooks.

In addition, try to specify the expected learning outcome as “Intended Learning Objectives” – specific measurable abilities that the course is intended to convey. We will use Bloom’s revised taxonomy to describe the school’s objective – Appendix 1 has an illustration to reference

A student who completed this course is able to:

1. Formulate the mathematical equations of the power flow problem
2. Record the calculations of the power flow problem
3. Assess the results of the power flow problem

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Outline of Training Activity

In the first part, students are introduced to Jupyter Notebooks platform. Following this presentation, the participants upload and run the Power flow-Jupyter source file to the platform step by step. In the Ybus step, they are required to fill in the missing part of the code for the formulation of the matrix. Additionally, they fill in and submit a questionnaire with the results of each step of the power flow problem.

Evaluation approach

A questionnaire has been prepared to receive feedback from students. The participants expressed their view anonymously by evaluating topics such as content, relevance of the exercise with the course, presentation and implementation of the exercise and utility, using the 0-5 scale.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.3 Energy Analysis Tool for Microgrid and Islanded Systems

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

Energy Analysis Tool for Microgrid and Islanded Power Systems

Overview

Hosting partner: CRES

Co-organizing partners: N/A

Planned date (approximate): July 2021

Type of Activity: Education Tool

Contact: Evangelos Rikos, vrikos@cres.gr

Short Description

A description of the selection of topics, the hosting partners, intended audience and why the course is relevant to ERIGrid 2.0

This is a free license tool, which allows users to simulate the energy behavior of a microgrid or an autonomous power system under steady-state conditions.

The specific tool is highly relevant to the ERIGrid 2.0 because of the scenarios that are analyzed in the project. These scenarios emphasize a lot on the case of microgrids, whereas other scenarios investigated in the project, including energy communities, make the use of the specific tool highly relevant.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

Why is this training activity required? What specific outcomes of EG-2 are conveyed here?

Link to appropriate studies, directives, project ambition, etc.

The specific tool is useful as part of the simulation and co-simulation approaches implemented in the project. Since a large part of ERIGrid 2.0 is dedicated to the analysis of microgrids and distribution grids, the use of such a tool is highly relevant and important.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

As Training Objectives Describe the competences that should be conveyed to the learners in your technical perspective.

This module intends to familiarize the user with two aspects:

- Modelling and analysis of microgrids and autonomous power systems under steady-state conditions and

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

- Optimization of the system’s operation in terms of cost and Renewable Generation.

In addition, try to specify the expected learning outcome as “Intended Learning Objectives” – specific measurable abilities that the course is intended to convey. We will use Bloom’s revised taxonomy to describe the school’s objective – Appendix 1 has an illustration to reference

A student who completed this course is able to:

1. Understand the techno-economic aspects of microgrids and autonomous power systems such as the power systems of geographical islands
2. Implement this analysis in the simulation environment and obtain the necessary results

Outline of Training Activity

Describe here the key components and learning activities comprising the training activity. A time schedule can be included here if available.

The specific tool is provided in the form of an executable application that allows the user to design the microgrid topology via a Graphical Interface:

Through this interface environment the user can introduce specific resources and specify their parameters. Also, other scenario parameters can be introduced via this interface. The execution of the simulation tests provide specific results illustrated in separate screens such as the one below:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Results can also be exported in the form of data files for further processing.

Evaluation approach

How is the success of the training activity evaluated? Note EG-2 requests an evaluation only by the organizers (NA3-Training_Activity_Report_Form)

The success of the tool could be evaluated by the number of users/downloads of the application.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.4 Smart Grid Applications Leveraging Machine Learning Principles

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

Smart grid applications leveraging machine learning principles in R studio

Overview

Hosting partner: University of Cyprus (UCY) - FOSS Research Centre for Sustainable Energy

Co-organizing partners: -

Planned date (approximate): Autumn 2022

Type of Activity: Education tool

Contact: George Makrides, makrides.georgios@ucy.ac.cy

Short Description

The smart grid applications leveraging machine learning principles in R studio is an educational tool relevant to the topics of predicting the performance of solar photovoltaic systems and forecasting day-ahead generation leveraging advanced artificial intelligent (AI) principles. Specifically, it presents the use of data-driven machine learning principles for the implementation of solar-specific smart grid applications (digital twin predictive performance models and solar generation forecasting). A detailed step-by-step procedure is provided for the construction of high-performing data-driven predictive models for photovoltaic (PV) systems based on a supervised learning approach and leveraging different machine learning techniques (artificial neural networks, support vector regression, regression trees, etc.). The predictive models (derived using the R scripting statistical computing programming language) are benchmarked and optimized by varying the input features, learning regime and model hyperparameters. Finally, the application of the constructed models as a PV power plant digital twin (optimally performing virtual replica) and in solar generation forecasting (day- and hour-ahead forecasting) is verified using actual PV performance datasets and numerical weather predictions (NWP).

Hosting partner: UCY- FOSS Research Centre for Sustainable Energy.

Intended audience: Researchers in the fields of solar production forecasting and AI modeling for smart grid applications.

Lastly, the course is relevant to ERIGrid 2.0 since it provides the demonstration environment of smart grid concepts pertaining to renewable system digital twins, solar generation forecasting and application of AI-driven approaches in the smart grid domain.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

The motivation behind this educational tool is the transition towards a secure, cost-effective and environmentally sustainable energy supply by enhancing the innovation landscape for optimally planning and operating future grids using day-head forecasting as a key and cost-effective enabler. The educational tool thereby aligns to this trend by providing the demonstration environment for key enabling technologies such as AI-driven solar generation forecasting.

The specific outcomes of EG-2 conveyed include the:

- Validation of predictive models leveraging machine learning principles for digital twin modeling
- Demonstration of an accurately performing AI-driven day-ahead solar generation forecasting tool

Transitioning to a sustainable energy society and mitigating climate change effects through accelerated energy sector decarbonization is a recognised top priority of the European Union (EU) under the recent European Green Deal (EGD) climate-neutral initiatives to reduce emissions by at least 55% by 2030.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

This tool intends to:

- Design data-driven digital twin models for solar PV systems
- Apply NWP data and AI-driven principles for hour- and day-ahead generation forecasting
- Validate the performance of different machine learning techniques in digital twin modeling
- Demonstrate the performance of AI technologies for day- and hour-head solar PV production applications

A student who completed this course is able to:

1. Produce a coherent PV power plant digital twin predictive model
2. Examine historic PV production data and validate the performance of the predictive model
3. Comprehend the underlying configuration structures of AI-driven principles for solar generation forecasting

Outline of Training Activity

The key components of this educational tool include the predictive modeling framework and the demonstration of day- and hour-ahead PV production forecasting based on AI-driven principles.

The learning activities comprise of:

- Setup of PV power plant predictive model
- benchmarking of machine learning techniques for PV plant digital twin modeling
- Design of solar PV production forecasting tool
- Verification of tool based on historic PV power plant data

Evaluation approach

The success of the training activity will be evaluated by obtaining feedback from the participants through the completion of an evaluation questionnaire.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.5 Recent Research Trends in Engineering and Validating Cyber-Physical Energy Systems

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

Recent Research Trends in Engineering and Validating Cyber-Physical Energy Systems

Overview

Hosting partner: AIT

Co-organizing partners: IEEE Industrial Electronics Society (IES)

Planned date: 29.06.2021

Type of Activity: Webinar (in the IES webinar series)

Contact: Thomas Strasser, thomas.strasser@ait.ac.at; Filip Pröstitl Andrén, filip.proestl-andren@ait.ac.at

Short Description

A driving force for the realization of a sustainable energy supply is the integration of renewable energy resources. Due to their stochastic generation behaviour, energy utilities are confronted with a more complex operation of the underlying power grids. Additionally, due to technology developments, controllable loads, integration with other energy sources, changing regulatory rules, and the market liberalization, the system's operation needs adaptation. Proper operational concepts and intelligent automation provide the basis to turn the existing power system into an intelligent entity, a cyber-physical energy system. The electric energy system is therefore moving from a single system to a system of systems.

While reaping the benefits with new intelligent behaviours, it is expected that system-level developments, architectural concepts, advanced automation and control as well as the validation and testing will play a significantly larger role in realizing future solutions and technologies. The implementation and deployment of these complex systems of systems are associated with increasing engineering complexity resulting also in increased engineering costs. Proper engineering and validation approaches and tools are partly missing until now.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

This webinar that is held by the IEEE IES discusses and summarizes the main needs and requirements as well as the status quo in research and development related to the engineering and validation of cyber-physical energy systems. Also, validation examples and short demos are presented. Finally, research trends and necessary future activities are outlined.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Target group(s)

All ERIGRID 2.0 stakeholders (academia/research, industry, energy utilities, standardization, general public).

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

This module intends to show future energy systems' higher complexity in scenarios with different penetration levels of renewables. It also introduces the necessity of system-level design and validation approaches based on simulations and laboratory testing as well as the combination of them in a hardware-in-the-loop manner.

Outline of Training Activity

The webinar covers the following topics:

- Higher complexity in cyber-physical energy systems
- Engineering problems and needs
- Status quo in research and development
- Validating controllers for cyber-physical energy systems
- Example Demo

Evaluation approach

An evaluation of the webinar is planned by IEEE IES in the form of an online questionnaire.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.6 Mosaik 3.0 – Open Source Smart Grid Co-simulation Framework

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan <Mosaik 3.0>

Overview

Hosting partner: OFFIS
 Co-organizing partners: -
 Planned date (approximate): September 2021
 Type of Activity: Webinar
 Contact: Jirapa Kamsamrong (jirapa.kamsamrong@offis.de)

Short Description

Nowadays, co-simulation is a very useful tool to combine detailed models of different domains for multi-modal analyses, to integrate components with different software stacks, and to split the computational load of simulations between several machines. Among different all-purpose co-simulation frameworks, the open-source tool mosaik is special in the way that it focuses on high usability and simple simulation setups. However, some use cases, especially the combination of continuous dynamics with discrete events (e.g. cyber-physical systems that rely on communication), couldn't be supported efficiently. Mosaik 3.0 can support these hybrid scenarios, superdense time, and many other things with minimal interface adjustments.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

Smart grid incorporates different domains and multi-energy networks. To combined different simulations, Mosaik enables to reuse and combine existing simulation models and simulators to create large-scale Smart Grid scenarios. These scenarios can then serve as a testbed for various types of control strategies or other algorithmic solutions for future power systems. According to ERGrid 2 project objectives, it aims to support the research, technology development, and innovation of smart grid and smart energy system approaches. Especially, the working activity in ERIGrid 2 project of JRA 1 that aims to establish the reference scenarios for validations and upscaling and JRA2 to improve interconnecting (coupling) multiple instances of non-real-time simulators, real-time simulators, hardware-in-the-loop components, and physical laboratory equipment.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Hence, the holistic system integration and testing procedure can be performed by using co-simulation software. Mosaik is well-known among researchers and students for co-simulation platforms from a basic scenarios to sophisticated scenarios. The new release Mosaik 3.0 offers new features to improve discrete-event capabilities. This would allow both internal ERIGRID partners and external interested users for adapting the new features to their research. Therefore, the “New co-simulation features of Mosaik 3.0” webinar will introduce new features of Mosaik for interested users.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

This module intends to introduce new features of Mosaik co-simulation that aim for intended learning for interested users that have basic knowledge and experience with Mosaik. The expected learning outcome is the learners will obtain new features during the webinar with simple examples and demos. The participants are expected to adopt new features by themselves depending on the context starting from the synthesis of their problems and adapting to their models/research. In addition, Mosaik developers (i.e. presenters at the webinar) also provide support via <https://mosaik.offis.de/contact/> for further questions after the event.

A student who completed this course is able to:

- Intermediate and advanced participants can apply new features of Mosaik 3.0 to their work
- Basic users understand how to work with Mosaik 3.0

Outline of Training Activity

- Introduction of mosaik (including new mosaik 3.0 features)
- Tutorial and demos showing new mosaik 3.0 features
- Questions

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.7 Addressing the Growing Complexity of Power and Energy Systems through Interconnection of Geographically Distributed Research Laboratories

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

14-05-2023

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

Addressing the Growing Complexity of Power and Energy Systems through Interconnection of Geographically Distributed Research Laboratories

Overview

Hosting partner: University of Strathclyde (UoS)
Co-organizing partners: impossible

Planned date (approximate): 24/May/2022

Type of Activity: Webinar

Contact: Zhiwang Feng and Mazher Syed, zhiwang.feng@strath.ac.uk

Short Description

A description of the selection of topics, the hosting partners, intended audience and why the course is relevant to ERIGrid 2.0

This webinar titled “Addressing the Growing Complexity of Power and Energy Systems through Interconnection of Geographically Distributed Research Laboratories” will be delivered by Dr. Mazher Syed (UoS) as part of the Smart Grid Webinar Series 2022 organized by Smart Grid Operation Centre, IVE Engineering, Hong Kong.

The intended audience include (but are not limited to) students, academic researchers, and industrial engineers working on power system controls, real-time simulations and experimental validations.

This seminar will disseminate the research work undertaken as part of Task JRA2.2 of the ERIGrid 2.0 project.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

Why is this training activity required? What specific outcomes of EG-2 are conveyed here?
Link to appropriate studies, directives, project ambition, etc.

The limitations of a single research infrastructure to address the growing complexity of power and energy systems has been quite evident in the recent past. While geographically distributed simulations approach has been proposed as a potential solution, its recognition and adoption is quite limited. This seminar demonstrates the applicability and feasibility of geographically distributed real-time simulation techniques for the validation of complex power systems. The developments and advancements in

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ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

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enabling the optimized utilization of the real-time validation capabilities of the geographically distributed research laboratories realised within ERIGrid 2.0 project will be disseminated. This research outcome is a key enabler for addressing the simulation limitation of the single research infrastructure in investigating the power energy system with growing complexity.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Objectives (ILOs)

As Training Objectives Describe the competences that should be conveyed to the learners in your technical perspective.

- To inform of the state-of-the-art developments and breakthroughs in geographically distributed real-time simulations to support validation of complex power and energy systems.
- Demonstrate applications of techniques with real-world examples.

In addition, try to specify the expected learning outcome as “Intended Learning Objectives” – specific measurable abilities that the course is intended to convey. We will use Bloom’s revised taxonomy to describe the school’s objective – Appendix 1 has an illustration to reference

An audience that has attended this panel session will be able to:

- **Beginners:** Describe, discuss and relate to geographically distributed real-time simulation techniques: their functionality, applicability, and suitability for validation of complex power and energy systems.
- **Intermediate:** Identify scenarios where the presented techniques can be employed.
- **Expert:** Employ techniques for validation of complex power and energy systems.
- **Expert:** Criticize and propose advances to techniques through further research.

Outline of Training Activity

Describe here the key components and learning activities comprising the training activity. A time schedule can be included here if available.

This activity will be carried out in the form of a webinar as part of the Smart Grid Webinar Series 2022 organized by Smart Grid Operation Centre, IVE Engineering, Hong Kong. A brief outline of the webinar is presented below:

- A summary of modern power grid transformation and challenges
- An introduction of geographically distributed simulations (GDS)
- Taxonomy and examples of GDS
- Demonstration of current developments

Evaluation approach

How is the success of the training activity evaluated? Note EG-2 requests an evaluation only by the organisers (NA3-TrainingActivity-Feedback-Form)

No formal evaluation is planned, however, a qualitative assessment through audience participation and engagement can be undertaken.

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A.8 First Webinar of RICH Europe on Transnational and Virtual Access Opportunities (TA/VA)

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

First Webinar of RICH Europe on Transnational and Virtual access opportunities (TA/VA)

Overview

Hosting partner: AIT
 Co-organizing partners: HEU RICH Europe CSA RI Project of NCPs
 Planned date: 23.11.2022

Type of Activity: Webinar

Contact: Thomas Strasser, thomas.strasser@ait.ac.at

Short Description

Introduction and overview of the ERIGrid 2.0 validation, testing, and education services with a focus on the access program to potential access users.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

The training is required to provide general information about the project as well as the access program to potential access users.

Target group(s)

All ERIGrid 2.0 stakeholders (academia/research, industry, energy utilities, standardization, general public) with a focus on potential access users.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

This module intends to show the higher complexity of future energy systems and introduces the necessity of system-level design and validation approaches based on simulations and laboratory testing as well as the combination of it in a hardware-in-the-loop manner. Furthermore, details about the access program and how to apply for it are provided.

Outline of Training Activity

The activity consists of a brief overview presentation with a focus on the access program.

Evaluation approach

No evaluation is foreseen.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.9 Solar-plus-storage System Environmental and Performance Measurements

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

Virtual access to solar-plus-storage system environmental and performance measurements

Overview

Hosting partner: University of Cyprus (UCY) - FOSS Research Centre for Sustainable Energy

Co-organizing partners: -

Planned date (approximate): Autumn 2022

Type of Activity: Virtual Labs

Contact: George Makrides, makrides.georgios@ucy.ac.cy

Short Description

The solar-plus-storage system environmental and performance measurements virtual lab is an educational training activity relevant to the topics of distributed energy resource observability (solar photovoltaic and battery storage systems), digitalization of grid assets and real-time supervision using grid-edge programmable automation controllers and cloud-based interfaces. Specifically, it presents an overview of the performance and supervisory architecture, leveraging cloud-based system dashboards that stream real-time (1-sec resolution) data, for a smart photovoltaic and battery storage test-bench system installed at UCY microgrid. The acquired smart meter measurements (using Modbus TCP SunSpec protocols) include the voltage, frequency, power (apparent, active and reactive), inverter temperature, charging/discharging power and operational status of the solar-plus-storage system.

Hosting partner: UCY- FOSS Research Centre for Sustainable Energy.

Intended audience: Researchers in the fields of solar-plus-storage systems and grid modernization.

Lastly, the course is relevant to ERIGrid 2.0 since it provides the demonstration environment of smart grid concepts pertaining to real-time distributed energy resource observability using smart inverters and open-communication interoperability in smart grids.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

The motivation behind this activity is the transition towards a secure, cost-effective and environmentally sustainable energy supply by enhancing the innovation landscape for integrating renewable energy sources. The training activity thereby aligns to this trend by providing the demonstration environment for

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Transitioning to a sustainable energy society and mitigating climate change effects through accelerated energy sector decarbonization is a recognised top priority of the European Union (EU) under the recent European Green Deal (EGD) climate-neutral initiatives to reduce emissions by at least 55% by 2030.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

This module intends to:

- Design a cloud-based supervision system for solar-plus-storage systems
- Apply open-communication interoperability protocols to stream data from grid-edge devices
- Validate advanced controls for smart inverters
- Demonstrate the performance of programmable automation devices linked to cloud databases for grid asset observability

A student who completed this course is able to:

1. Produce a coherent architecture for the real-time observability of solar-plus-storage systems
2. Examine historic consumption and production data of the solar-plus-storage system
3. Comprehend the underlying configuration structures of automation controllers that leverage interoperability in smart grids

Outline of Training Activity

The key components of this training activity include the interoperability framework, architectural design and demonstration of the solar-plus-storage cloud-based supervisory system.

The learning activities comprise of:

- Setup of photovoltaic and battery storage smart inverter for open communications
- Configuration of a programmable automation device to connect to specific registers of the inverters
- Design of cloud-based databases and dashboards for the visualization of real-time data streams
- Validation of supervisory data streams and advanced controls

Evaluation approach

The success of the training activity will be evaluated by obtaining feedback from the participants through the completion of an evaluation questionnaire.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.10 UCY Microgrid Real-time Measurements

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

Virtual access to UCY microgrid real-time measurements

Overview

Hosting partner: University of Cyprus (UCY) - FOSS Research Centre for Sustainable Energy

Co-organizing partners: -

Planned date (approximate): Autumn 2022

Type of Activity: Virtual Labs

Contact: George Makrides, makrides.georgios@ucy.ac.cy

Short Description

The microgrid real-time measurements virtual lab is an educational training activity relevant to the topics of smart meter data acquisition in microgrids, distributed energy resource observability (solar photovoltaic and battery storage systems), digitalization of grid assets and real-time supervision using grid-edge programmable automation controllers and cloud-based interfaces. Specifically, it presents an overview of the supervisory architecture, leveraging cloud-based system dashboards that stream real-time (1-sec resolution) data, from smart meters installed within a commercial-scale microgrid, UCY microgrid. The acquired smart meter measurements (using Modbus TCP SunSpec protocols) include the voltage, frequency, power (apparent, active and reactive) and power quality parameters (total harmonic distortion and crest factors). Measurements of solar irradiance, wind speed and direction, and temperature from a smart weather station are also coupled to the data streams.

Hosting partner: UCY- FOSS Research Centre for Sustainable Energy.

Intended audience: Researchers in the fields of microgrids and grid modernization.

Lastly, the course is relevant to ERIGrid 2.0 since it provides the demonstration environment of smart grid concepts pertaining to real-time distributed energy resource observability using smart meters and open-communication interoperability in smart grids.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

The motivation behind this activity is the transition towards a secure, cost-effective and environmentally sustainable energy supply by enhancing the innovation landscape for balancing demand and generation through microgrids. The training activity thereby aligns to this trend by providing the demonstration environment for key enabling technologies such as battery storage systems and grid-edge asset digitalization for solar-powered microgrids.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

The specific outcomes of EG-2 conveyed include the:

- Validation of smart grid asset digitalization for real-time supervision
- Demonstration of a novel cloud-based tools for real-time observability

Transitioning to a sustainable energy society and mitigating climate change effects through accelerated energy sector decarbonization is a recognised top priority of the European Union (EU) under the recent European Green Deal (EGD) climate-neutral initiatives to reduce emissions by at least 55% by 2030.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

This module intends to:

- Design a cloud-based supervision system for microgrids
- Apply open-communication interoperability protocols to stream data from grid-edge devices
- Validate advanced controls for smart inverters
- Demonstrate the performance of programmable automation devices linked to cloud databases for grid asset observability

A student who completed this course is able to:

1. Produce a coherent architecture for the real-time observability of the microgrid
2. Examine historic consumption and production data of the microgrid
3. Comprehend the underlying configuration structures of automation controllers that leverage interoperability in smart grids

Outline of Training Activity

The key components of this training activity include the interoperability framework, architectural design and demonstration of the microgrid cloud-based supervisory system.

The learning activities comprise of:

- Setup of smart meters for open communications
- Configuration of a programmable automation device to connect to specific registers of the smart meters
- Design of cloud-based databases and dashboards for the visualization of real-time data streams
- Validation of supervisory data streams and advanced controls

Evaluation approach

The success of the training activity will be evaluated by obtaining feedback from the participants through the completion of an evaluation questionnaire.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.11 Environmental Measurements and PV Models

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

Virtual Access to Environmental Measurements and PV Models

Overview

Hosting partner: CRES

Co-organizing partners: N/A

Planned date (approximate): March 2022

Type of Activity: Education Tool

Contact: Evangelos Rikos, vrikos@cres.gr

Short Description

A description of the selection of topics, the hosting partners, intended audience and why the course is relevant to ERIGrid 2.0

The specific tool provides access to a set of environmental and operational data from the PV systems located on the CRES premises in Pikermi, Greece.

The use of this tool is very relevant to the ERIGrid 2.0 activities, especially the activities under the VA work package as well as the JRA activities that address the Data-as-a-Service topic.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

Why is this training activity required? What specific outcomes of EG-2 are conveyed here?

Link to appropriate studies, directives, project ambition, etc.

This tool familiarizes the user with the operating characteristics of PV systems in relation to the environmental conditions. Apart from the online access to data, the user can benefit from downloading time series data in *.csv format for post processing or use in other applications.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

As Training Objectives Describe the competences that should be conveyed to the learners in your technical perspective.

This module intends to familiarize the user with understanding the operating characteristics of PV systems under different environmental conditions.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

In addition, try to specify the expected learning outcome as “Intended Learning Objectives” – specific measurable abilities that the course is intended to convey. We will use Bloom’s revised taxonomy to describe the school’s objective – Appendix 1 has an illustration to reference

A student who completes this course is able to:

1. Understand the operating characteristics of PV systems under real conditions,
2. Further analyze data related to the PV operation.

Outline of Training Activity

Describe here the key components and learning activities comprising the training activity. A time schedule can be included here if available.

The specific tool is divided into the physical setup and the web interface. The physical setup, involves two PV systems installed at different locations at CRES as can be seen in the following picture:

Also, the meteorological data are provided by an experimental setup used for the long-term assessment of PV modules. This setup and the relevant sensors are shown in the following figure:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

The data are collected by a data logger and published online on a webpage. A screenshot of part of this webpage is shown below:

PV System At CRES's Parking Lot

The measurements concern a PV system of 4.845kWp system which is installed in a parking lot of CRES, at a tilt of 40° and South orientation.

(Drag an area for zoom, right click to reset. Measurements of a chart can be downloaded by clicking on the legend of the chart.)

Choose time period:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Evaluation approach

How is the success of the training activity evaluated? Note EG-2 requests an evaluation only by the organizers (NA3-Training_Activity_Report_Form)

Evaluation of the specific tool's success can be achieved by monitoring the visibility of the specific webpage

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.12 Microgrid Balancing Experiment

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan Remote Access to Microgrid Balancing Experiment

Overview

Hosting partner: CRES

Co-organizing partners: N/A

Planned date (approximate): February 2022

Type of Activity: Education Tool

Contact: Evangelos Rikos, vrikos@cres.gr

Short Description

A description of the selection of topics, the hosting partners, intended audience and why the course is relevant to ERIGrid 2.0

The specific tool is a laboratory exercise that involves the remote connection to the experimental microgrid of CRES, with the aim of conducting a simplified power balancing experiment.

The relevance of the specific tool to the ERIGrid 2.0 activities arises from two aspects: Firstly, the scenarios investigated by ERIGrid 2.0 include, to a large extent, microgrids, and thus, experimentation on a microgrid is very relevant. In addition, and this is the second aspect that makes this tool highly relevant, the remote use of RIs by users is one of the key aspects of the project, connected to the extended RI analysis. Towards this direction, the remote lab application by CRES provides useful insights to the project partners and third parties.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

Why is this training activity required? What specific outcomes of EG-2 are conveyed here?

Link to appropriate studies, directives, project ambition, etc.

The specific tool is useful as part of the ERIGrid 2.0 activities connected to VA and TA activities, as well as JRA activities that deal with the extended RI (remote lab connections, services, and applications). This activity allows the host RI to prepare the laboratory for connecting with other laboratories of the consortium and allows potential external users (TA applicants) to become familiar with the specific RI and motivate them towards using it through the TA activity.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

As Training Objectives Describe the competences that should be conveyed to the learners in your technical perspective.

This module intends to familiarize users with two aspects:

- Experimentation on the power balancing of microgrids
- Understanding and use of tools that enable the remote access to laboratories and, overall, the Internet-of-Things concept

In addition, try to specify the expected learning outcome as “Intended Learning Objectives” – specific measurable abilities that the course is intended to convey. We will use Bloom’s revised taxonomy to describe the school’s objective – Appendix 1 has an illustration to reference

A student who completed this course is able to:

1. Understand the operating characteristics of microgrids and balancing requirements
2. Understand and implement the toolset that enables the access and control to a facility that is part of the Internet-of-Things concept

Outline of Training Activity

Describe here the key components and learning activities comprising the training activity. A time schedule can be included here if available.

The specific tool is divided into the physical setup and the web interface. The physical setup, which is located at the CRES premises in Pikermi, Greece, is shown in the following figure:

As can be seen in the simplified diagram, the two types of power units used in this experiment are Photovoltaics and Battery Storage. The scope of the experiment is that the user should manually modify the active power set-point of the storage unit in order to balance the production from the PVs. In addition to the active power set-point, the user can activate or deactivate the PVs, when necessary and to adjust the reactive power of the Battery Inverter in order to allow for more available power capacity.

The Battery Inverter communicates with the central SCADA application (in Node-RED) via RS485/SMANet, whereas, for the operation/supervision of the PVs two ESP32 controllers are utilized. The latter controllers connect to the SCADA application via wifi access. Both the Battery Inverter and the ESP32 modules use MQTT in order to publish their data to a specific broker, which, in turn, communicates with the SCADA over the LAN. Inversely, control quantities from the SCADA are published to the same broker, and the DER units of the microgrid, functioning as subscribers, are

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

The remote user of the experiment can supervise and control the setup via the following web interface:

Evaluation approach

How is the success of the training activity evaluated? Note EG-2 requests an evaluation only by the organizers (NA3-Training_Activity_Report_Form)

Since this experiment involves actual laboratory equipment exposed on the Internet, the strategy followed is to be available only upon request. Therefore, the requests received via email will be the precise approach to evaluate the success of the specific tool.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.13 ERIGrid 2.0 – Connecting European Smart Grid Research Infrastructures

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan General Project Introduction

Overview

Hosting partner: AIT

Co-organizing partners: ---

Planned date: 17.11.2020 (update/extension on 21.11.2020)

Type of Activity: Video(s)

Contact: Thomas Strasser, thomas.strasser@ait.ac.at

Short Description

Introduction and overview of the ERIGrid 2.0 validation, testing, and education services provided by the coordinator AIT to the general public.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

The training is required to provide general information to the public in the form of a video.

Target group(s)

All ERIGrid 2.0 stakeholders (academia/research, industry, energy utilities, standardization, general public).

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

This module intends to show future energy systems' higher complexity in scenarios with different penetration levels of renewables. It also introduces the necessity of system-level design and validation approaches based on simulations and laboratory testing as well as the combination of them in a hardware-in-the-loop manner. It also introduces the access activities of the project.

Outline of Training Activity

The activity consists of a brief overview video.

Evaluation approach

No evaluation is foreseen.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.14 Virtual tour through the SysTec Lab

ERIGRID 2.0 Training Activity Plan Virtual Lab Tour Fraunhofer IEE SysTec

Overview

Hosting partner: Fraunhofer IEE

Co-organizing partners: internal - ; external: Kassel University, Fraunhofer ISE and University of Freiburg

Planned date: 2021-09-22

Type of Activity: Virtual Laboratory Tour through the test center SysTec of Fraunhofer IEE

Contact: Dr. Gunter Arnold, gunter.arnold@iee.fraunhofer.de

Short Description

The Virtual Laboratory Tour through the test center SysTec of Fraunhofer IEE will be part of the “Wind and Solar Synergy Week” primarily organised by Fraunhofer IEE, Fraunhofer ISE and the Universities of Kassel and Freiburg for Master students of the “Online MSc. Wind Energy Systems and Solar Energy Engineering”. The virtual lab tour is scheduled for around 1.5 h and will take place on Wed. 22. Sept. 2022 at 4 pm CEST.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

This training activity seems to be important for the online master students in order to get an impression which lab infrastructure and components are necessary for addressing of R&D questions in the context of smart grids and DER grid integration.

Target group(s)

The target group for this training activity are primarily master students in the online master course WES-online.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

This module intends to provide a brief overview for students in the online Master course WES-online, how different characteristics (grid code compliance, performance, etc.) of DER units and smart grid components can be assessed, validated and demonstrated in a lab infrastructure.

A student who completed this virtual lab tour is able to:

1. Understand the needs for testing of smart grid components in a lab infrastructure
2. Describe the major components of a smart grid lab infrastructure.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Outline of Training Activity

The virtual lab tour provided a brief overview of different testing facilities at the test center SysTec located at Fraunhofer IEE, Kassel / Germany:

- PNI – Testing Laboratory for Grid Integration
- Mobile UVRT/ OVRT Testing Equipment
- HST – Hybrid System Test Field
- TPE – Test Center for Electromobility with PHIL test setup
- EMA – Electrical Machines Laboratory

The virtual lab tour is planned for around 1.5 h.

Evaluation approach

The success of this virtual lab tour will be evaluated by the hosting organizations e.g. based on the oral and written feedback during the Q- A-session.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.15 Advanced Real-time Supervision and Centralised Control of Distributed Energy Resources in Smart Grids

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

Advanced real-time supervision and centralized control of distributed energy resources in smart grids

Overview

Hosting partner: University of Cyprus (UCY) - FOSS Research Centre for Sustainable Energy

Co-organizing partners: -

Planned date: Winter 21

Type of Activity: Tutorial

Contact: George Makrides, makrides.georgios@ucy.ac.cy

Short Description

The advanced real-time supervision and centralized control of distributed energy resources (DERs) in smart grids is a tutorial relevant to the topics of grid modernization for high renewable shares and optimal operational management of DER in smart grids. The training activity scopes to present the latest digitally-enhanced methods and technologies used to enable the necessary observability and centralized control of underlying DER assets in smart grids. The training will specifically focus on the application of edge computing programmable automation controllers (PACs) and high-speed cloud-based systems for enhanced real-time energy management interoperability in smart grids.

Specifically, it describes the main interfaces of DER interoperability in smart grids and presents the use of data information models for the implementation of supervisory and control functionalities (e.g., active and reactive power set-points, Volt-VAR, Volt-Watt). The training activity further provides a conceptual overview of real-time supervision and control open-communication protocols, grid-edge IoT devices and cloud databases focusing on the UCY-FOSS nanogrid pilot. To this end, the use of communication interfaces and universal connectors to standard protocols (i.e., Modbus TCP) for interoperability will be extensively described.

Finally, the training activity is relevant to ERIGrid 2.0 since it provides the demonstration environment of smart grid concepts pertaining to renewable energy source (RES) and DER interoperability, real-time observability of future power systems and the applications of centralized supervision and control in the smart grid domain.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

The motivation behind this activity is the transition towards a sustainable energy supply and the requirement to implement cost-effective smart-grid solutions for the real-time supervision and control of interconnected inverter-based technologies, which are increasingly challenging the operation of conventional power systems (centralized vs de-centralized supervision). The training activity thereby aligns to this trend by presenting the interoperability requirements and demonstrating key enabling technologies such as grid-edge controllers for DER, asset digitalization and cloud-based centralized management.

The specific outcomes of EG-2 conveyed include the:

- Validation of smart grid asset digitalization for real-time observability.
- Demonstration of a novel grid-edge controllers and cloud-based tools for real-time supervision and control.

Transitioning to a sustainable energy society and mitigating climate change effects through accelerated energy sector decarbonization is a recognized top priority of the European Union (EU) under the recent European Green Deal (EGD) climate-neutral initiatives to reduce emissions by at least 55% by 2030 compared with 1990 levels.

Target group(s)

- Undergraduate students following courses in smart grids and RES.
- Researchers in the fields of smart grid applications and grid integration of RES.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

This tutorial intends to:

- Present concepts of smart inverter controls and interoperability protocols.
- Illustrate the architecture of cloud-based supervision systems for DER assets in smart grids.
- Demonstrate the performance of grid-edge programmable automation devices linked to cloud databases to stream data for grid asset observability.

A student who completed this course is able to:

1. Design data information models for smart inverter supervision and control.
2. Construct interoperability interfaces and validate the performance of programmable automation devices for DER management.
3. Comprehend the underlying configuration structures of smart-grid solutions for the real-time supervision and control of interconnected inverter-based technologies.

Outline of Training Activity

The key components of this training activity include the description of smart grid interoperability frameworks, DER flexibility, data information models and demonstration of the centralized real-time supervision and control system at a nanogrid pilot.

The learning activities comprise of:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

- Description of DER flexibility functions and interoperability protocols.
- Setup of data information models for smart inverters based on open communication protocols and standards.
- Configuration of a programmable automation device to connect to specific registers of smart inverters based on SunSpec protocol.
- Validation of supervisory data streams and advanced controls to the nanogrid pilot.

Evaluation approach

The success of the training activity will be evaluated by obtaining feedback from the participants through the completion of an evaluation questionnaire.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.16 Massive Open Online Course: Seminars 1-6

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan (1) Introduction to the course

Overview

Hosting partner: AIT

Co-organizing partners: ---

Planned date: 17.07.2023

Type of Activity: MOOC (video)

Contact: Thomas Strasser, thomas.strasser@ait.ac.at

Short Description

Introduction and overview of the ERIGrid 2.0 validation, testing, and education services provided by the coordinator AIT to the general public.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

The training is required to provide general information to the public and specially to engineers and researchers that are active in the domain of power and energy systems in the form of a video and presentation for the MOOC course.

Target group(s)

All ERIGrid 2.0 stakeholders (academia/research, industry, energy utilities, standardization, general public).

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

This module intends to show the higher complexity of future energy systems in the form of scenarios with different penetration levels of renewables. It also introduces the necessity of system-level design and validation approaches based on simulations and laboratory testing as well as the combination of them in a hardware-in-the-loop manner. It also introduces the access activities of the project.

Outline of Training Activity

The activity consists of a brief overview video and presentation.

Evaluation approach

No evaluation is foreseen.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

14-05-2023

ERIGrid 2.0 MOOC Seminar Plan Multi-Energy Networks

Overview

Hosting partner: OFFIS

Co-organizing partners: TU Delft, AIT

Planned date (approximate): 01.01.2023

Contact: Jirapa Kamsamrong (jirapa.kamsamrong@offis.de)

Short Description

Multi-energy networks, principally resulting from coupling of multiple energy vectors to exchange of energy flexibility across sectors for example a synergy concept between thermal and electrical grid by utilizing the flexibility of heat pump and heat storage to provide energy services to power system operator. Traditional simulation tools only offers the monolithic approach implementation with a huge effort. Co-simulation offers a promising solution by combining available simulation tools from different domains, integrate components with different software stacks, and to split the computational load of simulations between several machines. The co-simulation frameworks "Mosaik" is an open source tool which focuses on high usability and simple simulation setups.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

The synergy between research activities on co-simulation of the ERIGrid 2 project is essential to further develop innovative education. The multi-energy networks benchmark model developed in JRA 1.1 and the multi-domain co-simulation framework in JRA 2.1 are incorporated into this training module. This MOOC module provides co-simulation knowledge which students should have basic knowledge of programming. Students are expected to gain knowledge of the importance and necessity of co-simulation as well as performing simulations which they can develop further in their studies and research after finishing this course.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Objectives (ILOs)

This MOOC module provides three parts:

- Multi-Energy Networks Part I: Co-Simulation introduction by Prof. Dr. Peter Palensky (TU Delft)
- Multi-Energy Networks Part II: Co-Simulation with mosaik by Jan Sören Schwarz (OFFIS Institute)
- Multi-Energy Networks Part III: Example multi-energy network application by Dr. Edmund Widl (AIT)

1

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

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This MOOC module 2 intends to provide co-simulation knowledge with simple and realistic examples. Interested students can gain basic knowledge about the co-simulation framework and be able to practice by self-learning with simple examples and materials which are provided in this course. Also, real-life applications are provided in this module to enhance developing skills in co-simulation.

The learners are expected to solve the problems by using the knowledge provided in this course and be able to develop the skills by themselves. This module provides the background of how co-simulation is essential and how to get started. During the learning process, the students can learn from the examples by analyzing the model, creating new scenarios, solving the problem, and evaluating the results.

A student who completed this course can:

- Gain creative thinking on co-simulation framework
- Analyze baseline and develop alternative scenarios
- Perform co-simulation with simple models
- Evaluate the qualitative and quantitative results
- Develop skills in co-simulations with complex models

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

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ERIGrid 2.0 MOOC Seminar Plan

Power Hardware-in-the-loop Validation for Modern Power and Energy Systems

Overview

Hosting partner: ICCS (Nikos, Alexandros, Alkistis)

Co-organizing partners: UoS (Mazher, Zhiwang)

Planned date (approximate): December 2023

Contact: Alexandros Paspatis, agpaspat@gmail.com

Short Description

This seminar introduces the user to the Power Hardware-In-The-Loop (PHIL) testing methodology, utilized for the testing of smart grid components. Particularly, the advantages that PHIL brings with regards to flexibility of testing are initially discussed, followed by technical analysis focusing on the configuration of the required devices and the associated interface algorithms as well as the concerns regarding stability and accuracy of the PHIL setup.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

The requirements for testing of power system components have been substantially increased in the previous years with the realization of the smart grid scenario. Control and power devices serving multiple purposes and adhering to various and complex grid codes are needed today in our power systems. However, the testing of such devices still remains a challenging task, as direct field application may incur high costs and risks. Hence, laboratory validation is widely applied for smart grid components. In particular, for high power components such as inverters and electrical machines, the PHIL scenario arises, where a digital real-time simulator (DRTS) simulates the power system under consideration and the hardware device under test is interfaced with the simulated system through a power amplifier (PA). However, the relatively complicated setup consisting of the DRTS, the PA, the sensors and the interfacing cards, leads to accuracy and stability concerns for the PHIL testing procedure. This seminar aims to fill the educational gap in the above stated problem.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Objectives (ILOs)

This seminar intends to familiarize the student with the concept of Power Hardware-in-the-Loop testing. Based on ERIGrid 2.0 test cases, the seminar will first aim to motivate the student towards the applicability of PHIL testing, followed by an extended technical description of the required interface algorithms, the stability and accuracy constraints, as well as the limitation of the PHIL approach.

A student who completed this course is able to:

1. To define the properties and advantages of PHIL testing
2. To define the limitations of PHIL testing
3. To describe the most common interface algorithms for PHIL testing
4. To apply tools for the stability and accuracy analysis of PHIL setups

1

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

14-05-2023

ERIGrid 2.0 MOOC Seminar Plan

Geographically distributed real-time experiments for validation of (multi-)energy systems

Overview

Hosting partner: RSE

Co-organizing partners: RWTH, TUD

Planned date (approximate): Nov/Dec '23

Contact:

Vetrivel S. Rajkumar (V.SubramaniamRajkumar@tudelft.nl)

Enea Bionda (enea.bionda@rse-web.it)

Andres (RWTH)

Short Description

The increasing complexity of today's energy systems incorporating multiple energy sources calls for a distributed methodology to conduct experiments. This is because a single research infrastructure can rarely provide the required resources to study this complex system. The ability to study such systems is limited by the lack of multi-domain laboratories, detailed large-scale models, confidentiality reasons, and expertise. Hence, this lecture module covers the motivation, techniques/tools, and real-life demonstrations of geographically distributed real-time experiments to overcome some of these limitations. This includes techniques for simulations, co-simulations using cloud and edge solutions in a cyber secure manner.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

The ability to study modern cyber-physical power systems is limited by the lack of multi-domain laboratories, detailed large-scale models, confidentiality reasons, and expertise. This lecture module will present the outcomes of WP12 on distributed lab middleware and WP13 on extended research infrastructures from the ERIGrid 2.0 project. This seeks to build upon and realize the concept of interconnected virtual research infrastructures within Europe.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Objectives (ILOs)

This MOOC module 4 seeks to motivate the need for multi-Ri experiments, along with some outcomes from the JRAs. Furthermore, applications of specific lab-coupling software tools such as JanDER and VILLAS will be provided. Learners are expected to learn the concept of GD-RTS and distributed experiments. A student who completes this particular module can:

1

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

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1. Understand the motivation and behind multi-lab experiments
2. Analyze the results of multi-RI experiment
3. Evaluate the shortcomings of these approaches

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

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ERIGrid 2.0 MOOC Seminar Plan

Effective Design and Documentation of Complex Test System Setups – Practical Guidelines and Tools

Overview

Hosting partner: DTU

Co-organizing partners: AIT, CRES

Planned date (approximate): Jan '23

Contact: kheu@dtu.dk

Short Description

Smart energy systems solutions often involve several interactions between components, interfacing energy forms, and several engineering domains. For example, a smart voltage controller needs to be tested conjointly with the distribution grid and may rely on communications infrastructure. The characterization and validation of such solutions through testing, as well as the reproducibility of test results require a clear scoping of test conditions and purposes. The ERIGrid Holistic Test Description offers a means to facilitate this scoping and documentation of test plans.

This seminar will motivate where and why systematic test description is helpful, and introduce the basic concepts applied in test description. Via several examples, the basic concepts and their practical application is illustrated, covering the full range of HTD documentation from test case to experiment specification (example journey). The learning module is supported by learning tools such as a self-test quiz.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

The characterization and validation of smart energy solutions through testing, as well as the reproducibility of test results require a clear scoping of test conditions and purposes. To help the audience with this scoping and reproducibility efforts, the ERIGrid HTD tools and methods and related work in the field are introduced

(European policy context missing)

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Objectives (ILOs)

This seminar intends to convey tools to assist in scoping complex tests for clarity, interoperability and reproducibility.

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ERIGrid 2.0 MOOC Seminar Plan Industry's Opinion

Overview

Hosting partner: HEDNO (Christos, Panagiotis, Kostas)

Co-organizing partners: OCT (Ian)

Planned date (approximate): March 2023

Type of Activity: Seminar

Contact: Konstantinos Anastasakis (k.anastasakis@deddie.gr), Panagiotis Karafotis (p.karafotis@deddie.gr)

Short Description

An important goal of the ERIGrid 2.0 project is to capture the industry sector stakeholders' interest on the developed approaches, methodologies, and tools of the project. Thus, in this seminar is analytically presented the industrial community's opinion regarding the ERIGrid 2.0 developments, services and what they would like to adopt.

The seminar consists of two parts, in the first part is presented the perspective of a power systems expert for the above services. The following part is a brief analysis of survey results, regarding the latest developments on the holistic system validation approach, tools and methodologies for laboratory-based assessments and co-simulation as well as the provided Trans-national Access (TA) and Virtual Access (VA) programs. The survey questionnaire was distributed among industrial organizations, e.g. DSOs.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

Recognising the ongoing effort to accelerate the cooperation with industry is a potential challenge in order to allow early adoption of the developed principles for future testing and validation methods. Furthermore, the engagement of the industrial community active in the smart grid and energy systems research, testing, and validation domain in order to attract more industrial users to the ERIGrid 2.0 Research Infrastructures (RIs), is vital for the research community.

This seminar highlights the opportunities and benefits that the industrial community will gain through the integration of project developments, particularly DSOs, such as increasing transparency of grid services and modernising the complex structure of DSOs.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Target group(s)

- Researchers in the field of smart grid services and applications
- Energy Consultants in the industry sector

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

This seminar intends to familiarize the student with understanding the exchange of knowledge on smart grids in order to monitor the risks and opportunities of emerging technologies.

A student who completed this course is able to:

1. Obtain a general view of the project applicable to its concerns about control strategies, robustness, and cyber-security.
2. Identify the new technical challenges related to smart distribution grid.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Appendix B: Activity Reports

B.1 Webinar on Remote Testing & EIRIE Platform

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Report Remote Testing & EIRIE Platform

Overview

Hosting partner: DERlab

Co-organizing partners: University of Strathclyde, AIT, TECNALIA, DTU, RWTH, ICCS-NTUA, FOSS

Delivered date: 08 March 2021

Type of Activity: Webinar

Contact: leonard.ramos@der-lab.net

Agenda and Schedule of the event

- Welcome words from DERlab Board (Graeme Burt, Mohamed Shalaby)
- Overview of the ERIGrid 2.0 Research Infrastructure for Smart Grids and Smart Energy Systems (AIT / Thomas Strasser)
- Introduction of the ERIGrid 2.0 Lab Access Programme (TECNALIA / J. Emilio Rodriguez Seco)
- Experiences with Remote Lab Access Services on the Example VILLAS4ERIGrid (DTU / Kai Heussen)
- Virtual Research Services in ERIGrid 2.0 (RWTH Aachen / Steffen Vogel)
- Demo of the VLab Services from RWTH Aachen (RWTH Aachen / Steffen Vogel)
- Demo of the OpenAFPM Services from ICCS-NTUA (ICCS-NTUA / Kostas Latoufis)
- PANTERA project - A pan European Technology Energy Research Approach (FOSS / Venizelos Efthymiou)
- Q&A (DERlab / Mohamed Shalaby)

List of participants

List of participants		
Mohamed Shalaby	Maria Robowska	Isabel Alvite
Thomas Strasser	Felipe Jung	Tran-The Hoang
Shafi Khadem	Benedikt Leitner	Maria Trifiletti
Christina Papadimitriou	Artjoms Obusevs	Changhee Cho
Lorena Sánchez Relación	Darshan Gab'ndhi	Antonello Monti
Anna Mutule	Amelia Alvarez de Sotomayor	Marta Sturzeanu
Alexandros Tsitsanis	M Moiz	otilia bularca
Tasos Tsitsanis	Ahmad Niazi	Sophia Giovanett
Maria-Iro Baka	Vasileios Psaras	Rainer Bacher
Paula Carroll	Rais Mohamed Cherif	Guillaume GIRAUD
Theofilos Papadopoulos	Alexis Rey-Boué	Dagmar Jarásová

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

ERIGrid 2.0 partners showcased the project’s infrastructure and present the collected experiences with remote lab access. Also presented were the ERIGrid 2.0 Virtual Access to infrastructures with demos of two virtual facilities.

The PANTERA project presented the interactive multi-functional platform EIRIE that acts as the meeting point of all actors active in the field of energy research and innovation from all Europe.

Achievements and learning outcomes

Participants familiarized themselves with the scope of the ERIGrid 2.0 project, its Lab Access and Virtual Access programmes and their available physical and virtual facilities. The participants were able to witness the real-time demonstrations of two virtual services.

In addition, the participants were introduced to the PANTERA project, its objectives and the planned outcomes of the project.

To sum up, the participants were presented the scope of the projects and the opportunities they provide to the smart energy community. The participants also had the possibility to clarify any questions in the Q&A session, which was a valuable opportunity for potential ERIGrid 2.0 Lab Access applicants.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

B.2 Webinar on Recent Research Trends in Engineering and Validating Cyber-Physical Energy Systems

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Report

Recent Research Trends in Engineering and Validating Cyber-Physical Energy Systems

Overview

Hosting partner: AIT

Co-organizing partners: IEEE Industrial Electronics Society (IES)

Delivered date: 29.06.2021

Type of Activity: Webinar (in the IES webinar series)

Contact: Thomas Strasser, thomas.strasser@ait.ac.at; Filip Prösl Andrén, filip.proestl-andren@ait.ac.at

Agenda and Schedule of the event

The webinar covered the following topics:

- Higher complexity in cyber-physical energy systems
- Engineering problems and needs
- Status quo in research and development
- Validating controllers for cyber-physical energy systems
- Example Demo

List of participants (Only for Summer/Winter schools and workshops)

Around 30 participants joined the online event; due to GDPR regulations, the attendance list cannot be shared.

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

This webinar discussed and summarized the main needs and requirements as well as the status quo in research and development related to the engineering and validation of cyber-physical energy systems. Also, validation examples and short demos have been presented. Finally, research trends and necessary future activities have been outlined as well.

Achievements and learning outcomes

This module showed the expected future energy systems' higher complexity in scenarios with different penetration levels of renewables. It also introduced the necessity of system-level design and validation approaches based on simulations and laboratory testing as well as the combination of them in a hardware-in-the-loop manner.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Statistics of the event (Webinars or Virtual Workshops)

The following information about the webinar was made available by IES:

- No. of registered persons: 60
- No. of attendees: 30
- No. of project external persons: n/a

Feedback from participants (For activities that distributed questionnaires to participants)

An online questionnaire was distributed by IES, but the results have not been shared; therefore, no feedback information is available.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

B.3 Mosaik 3.0 – Open Source Smart Grid Co-simulation Framework

ERIGRID 2.0 Training Activity Report New Co-simulation features of Mosaik 3.0

Overview

Hosting partner: OFFIS

Co-organizing partners: -

Delivered date: 29.09.2021

Type of Activity: select one of: Webinar

Contact: Jirapa Kamsamrong (jirapa.kamsamrong@offis.de)

Agenda and Schedule of the event

11:00 - 11:30 Introduction of mosaik (including new mosaik 3.0 features)

11:30 - 12:10 Tutorial and demos showing new mosaik 3.0 features

12:10 - 12:30 Q&A

List of participants (Only for Summer/Winter schools and workshops)

Not applicable

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

Nowadays, co-simulation is a very useful tool to combine detailed models of different domains for multi-modal analyses, to integrate components with different software stacks, and to split the computational load of simulations between several machines. Among different all-purpose co-simulation frameworks, the open-source tool Mosaik is special in the way that it focuses on high usability and simple simulation setups. However, some use cases, especially the combination of continuous dynamics with discrete events (e.g. cyber-physical systems that rely on communication), couldn't be supported efficiently. This has completely changed with Mosaik 3.0, which supports these hybrid scenarios, superdense time, and many other things with minimal interface adjustments.

Achievements and learning outcomes

Advance participants familiar with Mosaik learn new features that can be applied to their research work.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Statistics of the event (Webinars or Virtual Workshops)

No. Registered persons: 43, No. of Attended Persons: 46, No. of Project External Persons: 32

- A. Insert a picture of the event video on YouTube or any other public repository (e.g. Zenodo)
<https://zenodo.org/record/5547934#.Yg2CJ-iZNEY>
- B. Insert photos of the event
Same as A

Feedback from participants (For activities that distributed questionnaires to participants)

In case a questionnaire was distributed to participants, please provide the results.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

B.4 First Webinar on RICH Europe on Transnational and Virtual Access Opportunities (TA/VA)

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Report

First Webinar of RICH Europe on Transnational and Virtual access opportunities (TA/VA)

Overview

Hosting partner: AIT

Co-organizing partners: HEU RICH Europe CSA RI Project of NCPs

Delivered date: 23.11.2022

Type of Activity: Webinar

Contact: Thomas Strasser, thomas.strasser@ait.ac.at

Agenda and Schedule of the event

The following table provides a high-level overview of the agenda of the RICH Europe Webinar:

Webinar		Speaker
10:00 - 10:10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation and welcome 	Dr. Daniele Gizzi – APRE RICH Europe Project Coordinator
10:10 - 10:50	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AHEAD2020 - Integrated Activities for the High Energy Astrophysics- Physics and Astronomy 	Dr. Salvatore Sciortino. INAF Osservatorio Astronomico di Palermo
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EVA-GLOBAL- European Virus Archive GLOBAL - Life sciences 	Dra. Christine PRAT. European Virus Archive Global
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ERIGrid 2.0- European Research Infrastructure supporting Smart Grid and Smart Energy Systems Research, Technology Development, Validation and Roll Out – Engineering and Energy 	Dr. Thomas I. Strasser. Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH (AIT)
10:50 – 11:00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LASERLAB-EUROPE - The Integrated Initiative of European Laser Research Infrastructures- Material Sciences & Analytical Facilities 	Dra. Sylvie Jacquemot. Ecole Polytechnique LASERLAB-Europe EU project.
	Q&A session	All speakers

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

List of participants (Only for Summer/Winter schools and workshops)

Around 65 participants joined the online event; due to GDPR regulations, the attendance list cannot be shared.

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

This module showed the expected higher complexity of future energy systems and introduces the necessity of system-level design and validation approaches based on simulations and laboratory testing as well as the combination of it in a hardware-in-the-loop manner. Furthermore, details about the access program and how to apply for it have provided.

Achievements and learning outcomes

The activity consisted of a brief overview presentation with a focus on the access program.

Statistics of the event (Webinars or Virtual Workshops)

The following information about the webinar was made available by RICH Europe:

- No. of registered persons: n/a
- No. of attendees: 65
- No. of project external persons: n/a

Feedback from participants (For activities that distributed questionnaires to participants)

No evaluation has been carried out.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

B.5 Virtual Tour through the SysTec Lab

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Report Virtual Lab Tour Fraunhofer IEE SysTec

Overview

Hosting partner: Fraunhofer IEE

Co-organizing partners: internal - ; external: Kassel University, Fraunhofer ISE and University of Freiburg

Delivered date: 2021-09-22

Type of Activity: Virtual Laboratory Tour through the test center SysTec of Fraunhofer IEE

Contact: Dr. Gunter Arnold, gunter.arnold@iee.fraunhofer.de

Agenda and Schedule of the event

The Virtual Laboratory Tour through the test center SysTec of Fraunhofer IEE was part of the “Wind and Solar Synergy Week” primarily organised by Fraunhofer IEE, Fraunhofer ISE and the Universities of Kassel and Freiburg for Master students of the “Online MSc. Wind Energy Systems and Solar Energy Engineering”. The virtual lab tour was scheduled for around 1.5 h and took place on Wed. 22. Sept. 2022 at 4 pm CEST.

List of participants (Only for Summer/Winter schools and workshops)

Not available

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

The virtual lab tour provided a brief overview of different testing facilities at the test center SysTec located at Fraunhofer IEE, Kassel / Germany:

- PNI – Testing Laboratory for Grid Integration
- Mobile UVRT/ OVRT Testing Equipment
- HST – Hybrid System Test Field
- TPE – Test Center for Electromobility with PHIL test setup
- EMA – Electrical Machines Laboratory

Achievements and learning outcomes

The main outcome of the virtual lab tour was to provide a brief overview to students in the online Master course WES-online, how different characteristics (grid code compliance, performance, etc.) of DER units and smart grid components could be assessed, validated and demonstrated in a lab infrastructure.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Statistics of the event (Webinars or Virtual Workshops)

Statistics of the virtual lab tour:

- No. Registered persons: 19
- No. of Attended Persons: 13
- No. of Project External Persons: 11

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Feedback from participants (For activities that distributed questionnaires to participants)

No questionnaire was distributed to the participants.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Consortium

Disclaimer

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